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Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Full name
AI	Artificial intelligence
API	Application programming interface
BMS	Battery management system
CAN	Controlled area network
CBC	COIN-OR Branch and Cut Solver
CE	Circular economy
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CPS	Cyber-Physical Systems
D	Deliverable report
DBT	Digital battery passport
DC	Direct current
DGA	Data Governance Act
DLT	Distributed ledger technology
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessments
DPP	Digital product passport
DSA	Digital Services Act
DT	Digital twin
DTLS	Datagram Transport Layer Security
ECMs	Equivalent circuit models
EPSG	European Petroleum Survey Group
ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation
EU	European Union
EV	Electric vehicle
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GD	GreenDelta GmbH
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPRS	General Packet Radio Service
GSM	Global System for Mobile Communications
IoT	Internet of Things
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KVC	Key value chain
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LIBS	Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy

LIFT	Lifecycle Information Framework Technology
ML	Machine learning
MILP	Mixed Integer Linear Programming
MQTT	Message queuing telemetry transport
NFC	Near-field communication
NIR	Near-infrared
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
RFID	Radio-frequency identification
RGB	Red, green, blue
SDU	Syddansk Universitet
SE	Stakeholder engagement
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
SoC	State of Charge
SoH	State of Health
SPA	Single Page Application
TARTU	Tartu Linn (Tartu City)
TJT	Tallinna Jäätmete Taaskasutuskeskus AS
TLN	Tallinna Linn (City of Tallinn)
TLS	Transport Layer Security (protocol)
UI	User Interface
UPI	Unique product identifier
URL	Unique resource location
UX	User Experience
VAT	Value-added tax
XRF	X-ray Fluorescence
XRT	X-ray Transmission

Executive Summary

This report details the outcomes from two distinct yet complementary tasks within the TREASoURcE project, focusing on the enablement of Circular Economy (CE) transitions: Task 6.3, investigating Digitalization solutions, and Task 6.4, applying Spatial and Logistics Optimization to the specific case of household biowaste management in Tallinn, Estonia. The analyses explore the potential of digital tools to enhance circularity across various value chains and demonstrate a practical application of optimization for improving resource allocation and logistical efficiency in a real-world urban system.

Task 6.3: Digitalization examines seven digital solutions that enable the transition from linear to circular economy models, addressing challenges in resource optimization, waste reduction, and stakeholder collaboration. The following solutions were studied:

- **Digital Product Passports:** Structured data repositories that provide transparency and traceability throughout product lifecycles, enabling informed decision-making for manufacturers, service providers, consumers, and recyclers.
- **Digital Twin Technology for Circular Battery Value Chain:** IoT-based digital replicas that enhance EV battery lifecycle management, optimizing repurposing and recycling processes while supporting performance and safety monitoring.
- **Digital Marketplaces:** Online platforms facilitating material exchange and circular trade by centralizing information, reducing transaction costs, and enhancing transparency across value chains.
- **Digital Waste Sorting Systems:** AI, advanced sensors, and robotics are applied transform complex waste stream handling, improving material recovery rates and sorting precision.
- **Sensor-Based System For Waste Collection Optimization:** IoT-enabled monitoring and algorithmic route planning significantly improve operational efficiency in municipal waste management, reducing fuel consumption and emissions.
- **Recycling Education Software:** User-friendly applications enhance awareness and participation in recycling through personalized learning and gamification approaches.
- **Personal Carbon Footprint Calculators:** Tools that quantify environmental impacts of individuals and empower users to adopt more sustainable practices.

Moreover, the landscape of EU data protection and sharing regulations was explored. In specific, key principles and measures for compliance with EU's General Data Protection Regulation, Data Governance Act, Data Act and Digital Services Act were studied.

The studied solutions share key characteristics that enable circular principles: enhancing information transparency, facilitating stakeholder collaboration, providing dynamic management capabilities, and supporting behavioral change. Despite implementation challenges related to costs, technological complexity, and data standardization, these digital technologies demonstrate significant potential to accelerate the transition to a sustainable, resource-efficient economy. Successful implementation requires interoperability, user-centered design, coordination among value chain actors, and compliance with data protection and sharing regulations in the EU context.

Task 6.4: "Spatial and Logistics Optimization" focused on managing household biowaste in Tallinn by applying principles of accurate data, efficient information flow, and optimized resource management. This task developed a detailed methodology to model the supply of biowaste, using current monthly estimates (approximating 2024 conditions based on April/October 2024 data) and future projections for 2035 and 2050 under Business-As-Usual (BAU), Market-driven, and City-oriented scenarios derived from official population forecasts. This supply was then matched against the demand (processing capacity) of designated Biogas (EKT Ecobio Biogas plant) and Composting (TJT Waste Recycling Centre) facilities, which included an assumed planned capacity expansion of +25% for 2035 and +50% for 2050. The core of this task involved pre-processing detailed household data (geocoding, population-weighted waste disaggregation, and linking to pre-calculated network distances and nearest OpenStreetMap nodes), followed by K-Means clustering of households (respecting operational constraints of 250 addresses/26 tons via splitting and merging) and assignment of representative points. A Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model was then employed to optimize the allocation of these clusters to facilities, aiming to maximize total monthly system profit (defined as facility revenue minus transport costs, using pre-calculated distances and a round-trip transport cost of €0.07/ton·km). Post-optimization, specific routes and their NetworkX-calculated lengths were determined.

The results for the Tallinn biowaste optimization demonstrated substantial improvements over a baseline district-based allocation. For the ~2024 baseline waste data, spatial optimization nearly doubled the estimated monthly profit (from approximately €8,700 to €16,100) and reduced total monthly transport costs by around 13%. This was primarily achieved by ensuring 100% utilization of the high-revenue Biogas plant, which was only 30% utilized under the static district rules. Across all six future scenarios (2035 and 2050), the optimized system maintained profitability, yielding monthly profits between €19,200 and €22,900. A critical finding was that the Biogas plant's capacity consistently emerged as the primary limiting factor, operating at or near its expanded capacity limit in all future scenarios. Consequently, the Composting facility remained significantly underutilized, primarily processing overflow waste. Average one-way route distances for optimized assignments were remarkably stable across scenarios, averaging ~15km for Biogas and ~23km for Compost.

Furthermore, Task 6.4 also focused on optimizing a Fix and Repair Shop network for the city of Tartu, Estonia. Through a survey, a stakeholder workshop, and spatial analysis considering population density and accessibility, an optimal network of 5-7 workshops was proposed. This work also explored integrating repair functions into existing waste stations and innovative mobile repair solutions, aiming to increase citizen awareness and access to repair services, thereby promoting reuse and resource conservation.

In synthesizing the outcomes of both tasks, this report underscores that digitalization provides the essential data infrastructure and tools for modern CE practices, while spatial and logistics optimization offers the analytical capabilities to translate this data into efficient and economically sound operational strategies. The Tallinn case study clearly illustrates this synergy, revealing significant potential for enhancing current systems and providing quantitative insights for future planning and the replicability of circular innovations. Key takeaways include the critical importance of accurate local data, validated economic

parameters (especially transport costs), strategic capacity planning for high-value facilities, and the adoption of consistent data and modeling approaches for robust decision-making in the transition towards a circular economy.

1 INTRODUCTION

The TREASoURcE project (2022-2026, <https://treasource.eu/>) aims to initiate systemic change by developing and demonstrating circular economy (CE) solutions for currently underutilized or unused resources, specifically targeting plastic waste, end-of-life electric vehicle (EV) batteries, and bio-based waste and side streams across diverse urban and regional contexts. By implementing these solutions in collaboration with companies, civic society (including citizens, consumers, and regional actors), and field experts, TREASoURcE aims to significantly enhance product and material circulation, particularly within the Nordic and Baltic Sea Regions. A core tenet of this endeavour is the recognition that the replicability and sustainability of CE innovations depend on robust logistical frameworks and the strategic/ effective use of digital technologies to manage complex material flows and optimize integrated value chains.

The advancement of digital technologies offers transformative potential for enhancing the efficiency, transparency, and coordination required for successful CE implementation. In Chapter 2 of this report, the outcomes of the review conducted on digital solutions that support CE are presented. The digital solutions were studied primarily by reviewing scientific literature, technical reports, industry reports and whitepapers, as well as relevant regulations. The review aimed to provide an overview of significant digital solutions supporting CE and stakeholder engagement. The key principles and technologies of each solution are described and explained, with the focus on supporting the implementation, highlighting the success factors for replication of these solutions. Moreover, benefits created by implementing these solutions are discussed. In addition, regulatory landscape related to digital solutions is explored and key steps for compliance are formulated. The following solutions are studied in Chapter 2:

- Digital twin technology for circular battery value chain
- Digital product passport
- Digital marketplace
- Digital waste sorting system
- Sensor-based system for algorithmic optimization of the waste collection
- Software for recycling education
- Personal carbon footprint calculator

Similarly, the logistical complexities associated CE transition especially with source-separated biowaste collection are substantial [1]. Spatial optimization, a field leveraging operations research, geographical analysis, and computational methods, provides indispensable tools for addressing the complex logistical challenges associated with CE implementation within a defined geographic space [2]. In chapter 3 of this report, we showcase the application of quantitative modeling to a real-world problem: the allocation of Tallinn's household biowaste to designated biogas and composting facilities. As highlighted within the TREASoURcE framework, a critical factor for the replicability of CE innovations is the effective matching of supply (biowaste generation) with demand (facility processing capacity). This task develops a supply-demand matching model based on spatial characteristics, regional socio-demographic forecasts [3], and economic parameters. It employs spatial optimization techniques to determine allocation strategies that maximize economic profit under various current and future scenarios (2035 and 2050), considering operational constraints and dynamic facility capacities. The aim is to provide decision support regarding the feasibility and operational design of Tallinn's biowaste system and inform potential "deployment go-no-go" triggers for similar initiatives. Furthermore, Task 6.4 also focused on optimizing a Fix and Repair Shop network for the city of Tartu, Estonia, highlighting another dimension of logistical planning for CE.

This report, therefore, synthesizes findings from both the broad landscape of digital CE solutions and a deep-dive application of spatial optimization to biowaste management, offering insights relevant to the strategic goals of the TREASoURcE project.

2 Task 6.3 Digitalization Outcomes

2.1 Introduction

The transition from a linear to a circular economy (CE) is crucial for sustainable development, as it aims to minimize waste and optimize resource use. Digital technologies, including the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain, and digital marketplaces, play a pivotal role in this transition by enhancing efficiency, transparency, and collaboration across various sectors [4].

This literature review focuses on digital solutions that support the CE. The motivation for this study stems from the growing recognition of digital technologies' transformative potential in advancing CE practices. Recent research has highlighted how digital solutions can drive resource optimization, waste reduction, and overall sustainability [5]. By leveraging these technologies, organizations can overcome challenges, innovate, and accelerate progress toward a more sustainable and CE [6]. This review aims to provide an understanding of how these digital solutions can be implemented.

In the first phase of the review, the solutions under review were identified based on information from primary and secondary sources. To collect information from primary sources, a workshop with expert project partners was held, where digital solutions supporting CE were ideated and evaluated based on their importance and relevance. Four solutions were identified in this way. To extend the list of studied solutions, a list of digital solutions supporting CE was formulated by reviewing scientific literature. The final list of solutions was then formulated by extending the list of solutions deemed most relevant by project partners by adding the solutions found most relevant by scientific literature.

In the second phase of the review, the identified solutions were studied by reviewing scientific, technical and industrial reports and whitepapers. The main aim of the review is to provide guidance for implementation of the studied solutions, with the main focus on the technical aspects. Therefore, the review process focused on several aspects of the digital solution that facilitate understanding of them and guide their implementation. In specific the following points were selected to be addressed by the review:

- **General description:** To relay essential understanding of the solutions, the key technological and operation principles of each digital solution are formulated.
- **Relation to CE and benefits:** The role each solution plays in supporting CE is explored, along with benefits generated by deploying the solution.
- **Implementation:** Implementation steps, challenges and success factors are detailed for each solution.

Moreover, regulatory landscape related to digital solutions is explored in a separate subchapter, supporting compliance with the EU regulations related to data handling.

In particular, the following solutions are studied:

- Digital product passport
- Digital twin technology for circular battery value chain
- Digital marketplace

- Digital waste sorting system
- Sensor-based system for algorithmic optimization of the waste collection
- Software for recycling education
- Personal carbon footprint calculator

The link of the studied solutions to CE and individual circular strategies is presented in *Figure 1*. Some of the selected solutions support a specific task within a CE ecosystem. For instance, digital waste sorting enhances the efficiency of the sorting process and enables higher quality of recycling. On the other hand, other studied solutions are supporting several CE tasks at once. For instance, digital marketplace reduces the information asymmetry between producers of end-of-life materials and products and potential operators of various CE solutions (e.g., recycling of plastics or reuse of second-life electronic equipment).

Figure 1: Overview of digital solutions studied in T6.3 and their relation to CE activities.

2.2 Regulatory landscape

Digital technologies are important for the CE, as they can facilitate optimizing waste collection, enabling DPPs, and educating consumers. However, these systems process data subject to EU law. In particular, operators must comply with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [7] as well as newer data governance laws and platform rules. This section reviews key EU regulations – GDPR, the Data Governance Act (DGA), the Data Act, and the Digital Services Act (DSA) – focusing on obligations and practical compliance for circular-economy applications. The regulatory landscape is explored with the focus on the relevance for the digital solutions studied in this report.

EU data law now comprises a “data strategy” portfolio. At its core, the *General Data Protection Regulation* (GDPR) [7] (effective May 2018) governs all personal data processing. In parallel, the *Data Governance Act* (DGA) [8] and *Data Act* [9] provide rules on data sharing and IoT data access, respectively, and the

new *Digital Services Act* [10] imposes obligations on online platforms and marketplaces. These are complemented by sector-specific rules (e.g. product regulations) and other digital laws.

2.2.1 GDPR: Core Principles and Controller Obligations

The GDPR applies to any processing of personal data in the EU, defining strict principles (lawfulness, purpose limitation, data minimization, storage limitation, integrity/confidentiality) and data-subject rights (access, erasure, portability, etc.) [11]. For digital circular-economy services, a key task is to identify what user or behavioral data count as personal data (names, contact info, device identifiers, location traces, household waste levels, app usage, etc.), and ensure every processing has a legal basis (e.g. consent or legitimate interest) [12]. Controllers and processors must implement “appropriate technical and organisational measures” and be able to demonstrate compliance [13]. In practice this means adopting Privacy by Design: pseudonymizing or anonymizing data streams wherever possible, encrypting data in transit/storage, and building data-minimization into system design [12].

For example, an IoT waste bin system should avoid capturing unnecessary personal detail; it may anonymize fill-level data by tagging bins with non-identifying codes. A citizen recycling app might use age- or interest-based grouping rather than exact birth dates. In all cases one must document DPIAs (Data Protection Impact Assessments) when processing is “high risk” (e.g. systematic profiling of households, video sorting analytics) and ensure the GDPR accountability principle (Art. 24) is met [13]. Controllers must also maintain records of processing (Art. 30 of GDPR) [14] and, if not based in EU, appoint an EU representative [15] (exemptions exist).

Key GDPR obligations and strategies:

- **Lawful basis and transparency:** Collect and process data only for specific, declared purposes; inform users via privacy notices; use consent or legitimate interest appropriately. For instance, a smart bin route-optimization service may rely on a municipal contract (public interest) or user consent to collect location-based bin data.
- **Data minimization and pseudonymization:** Only gather data strictly needed (e.g. bin level rather than who threw the trash) and apply techniques like hashing or tokenization. This aligns with Art. 25 GDPR (data protection by design) which explicitly calls for measures such as pseudonymization to implement data-minimization [12].
- **Security measures:** Implement encryption, access controls, and regular testing (consistent with Art. 32 GDPR) [16]. For networked IoT devices, follow secure-by-design guidelines and update software.
- **Data subject rights:** Ensure mechanisms for user access, correction, and deletion of personal data. For example, a recycling app must allow a user to view and delete their profile.
- **Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA):** Conduct DPIAs for novel high-risk systems (e.g. AI-based waste-sorting cameras, real-time citizen monitoring apps). This is required if large-scale profiling or monitoring of public areas is involved, or if special-category data might be inferred (Art. 35). DPIAs also support the GDPR accountability principle [13].

By integrating privacy safeguards from the start, operators can avoid costly redesign later and build user trust. The GDPR's accountability rules even encourage use of approved codes of conduct or certification schemes (Art. 40–42 of the regulation) where available.

2.2.2 Data Act

The EU Data Act (effective September 2025) [9] complements GDPR by regulating non-personal data and IoT-generated data. It grants *users of connected products* (including businesses and consumers) rights to access and share the raw data their devices generate, under fair contractual terms. For example, a waste collection service or citizen (as a product-user) will have the right to obtain data from waste sensors or smart meters. Conversely, it restricts IoT service providers from unilaterally blocking third-party access.

Under the Data Act, providers of connected devices (smart bins, etc.) must be able to supply a user's own raw usage data (sensor readings, timestamps, etc.) at no cost upon request [17]. Metadata needed to interpret the data (e.g. unit labels, GPS-encodings) must also be provided. Importantly, "derived" or proprietary analyses (e.g. predictive battery life models) are *excluded*, but clear demarcation is required. Operators should update their systems so that data can be exported securely (for example via a user portal or API) and transferred to third-party providers if the user wishes [17]. New products placed on the EU market after September 2026 must be designed for easy data access, with secure tools or interfaces allowing customers to obtain their data directly.

Practical implications of the Data Act

- IoT device makers (or their service integrators) must build in data export functions by design. For instance, a DPP should allow owners to download usage logs.
- Service operators should review contracts and terms: they cannot restrict the user's right to share device data with competitors or third parties. All data transfers must be secure and user-initiated.
- Even data held by cloud platforms (for AI or optimization services) falls under the Act: providers must enable data retrieval and transmission (often in an interoperable format).
- The Act also covers *business-to-business* and *public sector* data-sharing obligations (e.g. public bodies must share certain data with companies under fair conditions). Companies should map what industrial data they hold and prepare policies for sharing or licensing this data.

2.2.3 Data Governance Act

The Data Governance Act (DGA) (applied from Sept 2023) [8] focuses on fostering data sharing within the EU. It does *not* override GDPR, but rather creates a trust framework for voluntary data sharing, especially for non-personal or willingly donated personal data. Key features include [8]:

- **Data intermediation services:** Organizations that act as neutral brokers (platforms or intermediaries) can register under the DGA. They must adhere to strict neutrality and transparency rules.

Operators should ensure any third-party data marketplace they use is DGA-registered and follows best practices for trust and security.

- **Data altruism:** The DGA allows individuals or companies to voluntarily donate data “for the common good” (e.g. environmental research) without reward. Companies running citizen data-collection platforms (e.g. recycling tracking app) can consider registering as “data altruism organizations”. This gives them credibility and access to an EU registry of altruistic data hubs.
- **European Data Spaces:** The DGA envisions sector-specific data spaces. Operators can join these spaces to share standardized data (e.g. material flows, recycling rates) securely across borders. Participation often involves agreeing to common formats and trust frameworks, which can help with interoperability.

Compliance strategies under the DGA

- When setting up data-sharing services, design them for neutrality and allow user (data-holder) control. Avoid bundling additional services in a way that could conflict with neutrality rules.
- Use the EU Data Governance Act registry. If your company acts as a data intermediary or altruism organization, seek formal recognition by the DGA’s competent authority.
- Leverage common European data spaces by aligning your data models with their standards. For example, a DPP solution should fit the forthcoming EU DPP standards and could publish non-personal product data via a data space.
- Understand that while GDPR still protects personal data, the DGA encourages sharing of non-personal or consented data in a responsible way, e.g. anonymized waste generation statistics for research.

In short, the DGA promotes trustworthy sharing rather than imposing strict new limits. Compliance means choosing interoperable systems and trusted partners, and giving data subjects clear choices about altruistic sharing.

2.2.4 Digital Services Act

The DSA [10] (effective 2024) targets large online intermediaries, including marketplaces and apps. It introduces new obligations to combat illegal content/products and improve transparency. There are several requirements relevant for digital solution operators.

Digital marketplaces selling second-hand or recycled goods must verify business sellers (“Know Your Business Customer” or KYBC). The DSA requires marketplaces to collect and vet verification information (identity, VAT number, etc.) for new sellers and use best efforts for existing ones [18]. Marketplace interfaces must also clearly present any product safety or usage information required by EU law (e.g. compliance markings) [18]. Furthermore, platforms (including apps with user-generated content) must implement notice-and-action systems. Recipients must be able to flag illegal or copyrighted content, and platforms must evaluate reasons for removal and take action [18].

The DSA mandates clear, plain-language terms of service and requires each provider to designate EU points of contact for regulators (Article 11) and for end-users (Article 12) [18]. Non-EU providers need an EU-based legal representative (Article 27) for enforcement issues. Additionally, very large platforms (with > 45M EU users) must conduct systemic risk assessments (e.g. spread of illegal goods or disinformation) and submit to audits. While most SME projects fall below this threshold, any platform experiencing rapid growth should monitor this requirement.

Practical DSA compliance tips

- Prepare clear processes for content removal and appeals, especially if your service includes user uploads (e.g. community recycling tips or trade of waste materials). Document your moderation criteria and keep logs.
- Ensure the platform's terms of service explicitly outline rules for users and sellers; inform users of updates. Include special provisions for minors (the DSA bans targeted ads to under-18s) and for identifying any advertising content.
- Perform KYBC checks for marketplace sellers. This may require integrating identity-verification services or collecting official documents from sellers.
- Publish basic transparency reports, even if not mandated; this is seen as a best practice.

2.2.5 Compliance Strategies for Circular Solutions

In light of the above laws, operators of CE technologies should adopt a multi-layered strategy. Below we outline some of the measures to deploy when implementing the studied digital solutions.

- **Embed privacy in system architecture.** From concept to deployment, design systems to limit personal data collection. For IoT sensors, store only anonymized device IDs or aggregate metrics whenever possible. For citizen apps, collect only the minimum profile and usage data needed (e.g. a user's postal code, not full address, if location is required for regional recycling info). The GDPR explicitly requires implementation of measures like pseudonymization and data minimization [12].
- **Anonymize or aggregate data for analysis.** When using data for analytics (e.g. optimizing waste routes or generating a carbon footprint map), strip identifiers and coarsen granularity (e.g. neighbourhood rather than household). Always assess whether new derived data remain personal (GDPR Recitals 26, 28).
- **Default privacy settings.** Configure apps and user interfaces so that the default is maximum privacy: e.g., opt-in for any notifications or sharing features. Per Art. 25 of the GDPR, by default only necessary personal data are processed [12].
- **Encrypt sensitive data.** All personal data and IoT telemetry (especially when transmitted over wireless or stored in the cloud) should use current encryption standards. This protects against breaches and aligns with GDPR's integrity/confidentiality requirement [13].
- **Distinguish between IoT data and personal data.** IoT devices often generate mixed data (some personal, some not). Operators must carefully segregate data subject to GDPR. For example, a

location-based waste sensor might collect timestamps and GPS coordinates that qualify as personal data, the Data Act obliges sharing raw data, but GDPR still applies. The GDPR is not overridden – personal data extracted from device data (e.g. inferring which household’s bin is being emptied) remain protected.

- **Address the immutability of blockchain.** Many DPPs or IoT data ledgers use blockchain. This clashes with GDPR’s “right to erasure.” In practice, such systems should avoid putting personal data on-chain (store only product or IoT data and keep personal links off-chain). Operators should design DPP and blockchain solutions so that any personal information can be deleted or access-controlled without altering the entire chain.

2.3 Digital product passport

One of the key aspects of digitalization and its supporting role in the adoption of a CE is its ability to provide information and feedback on the performance of the implemented solutions [19]. Indeed, proper utilisation and generation of the data by means of digital technology is essential for the efficient implementation of a CE [20]. When a CE transition is carried out with the involvement of digital technologies, the technology of a digital product passport (DPP) emerges as a natural design choice. The deployment of this technology allows the stakeholders associated with a product’s value chain to communicate among themselves, exchanging information on materials and components of a product [21]. Thanks to this, the actors of the product’s value chain are able to optimize the product design considering its whole life cycle as well as trace the fate of product’s materials and components over the value chain [22]. In general, goals that can be achieved by the implementation can be summarized as [23]:

- Ensuring access to product related data for all stakeholders along the value chain
- Improving value chain collaboration
- Establishing transparency and traceability of product life cycle data, enabling compliance and standardisation
- Enabling critical material flows tracking
- Enabling the implementation of circular strategies
- Benchmarking of various products

The DPP can be conceptualized as a digital certificate technology that provides information on the product in question as it moves through the individual steps of its value chain [21]. The DPP is based on the creation of the digital identity of a product. This digital identity then enables the stakeholders associated with the value chain to verify the authenticity of the product and the claims made about the product [24]. The DPP aims to enhance transparency and traceability within supply chains, thereby enabling stakeholders—including manufacturers, consumers, and recyclers—to make informed decisions regarding product management and sustainability [25].

Key components

A framework for the implementation of a DPP for a CE was proposed that structures DPP systems into three layers [21], as visualised in Figure 2:

- Layer 1: Data Collection
- Layer 2: Data Curation and Sharing
- Layer 3: Data Leverage

Figure 2: Visualization of the layers of the digital product passport.

The *Data Collection* layer generally represents the technology deployed in the physical environment that records the information on the attributes of the product and converts them to a digital format. This layer typically makes use of technologies such as sensors and Internet-of-Things (IoT). The *Data Curation and Sharing* layer facilitates the processing and organisation of the data collected in Layer 1, as well as the accessibility to this data by the actors associated with the DPP system. The Layer 2 utilises technologies such as machine learning and AI, cloud technologies, and blockchain. The *Data Leverage* layer represents the interaction between the DPP and its final user. The final user can be either an individual consumer or an organisation. The Data Leverage layer can be enabled by the use of blockchain technology, e.g., features such as smart contracts or tokenization [21].

The content of a DPP is of high importance for its function as a CE enabler. In general, it should contain information on the life cycle stages of a product as well as detailed information on the manufacturing processes that generated and maintained the product over its life cycle [26]. However, the specific content requirements depend on the sector that the product belongs to and several other product-specific criteria such as product or lifecycle complexity, its value and potential harm [23]. Typically, most DPPs are produced during the production stage but they can also be generated later on in the life cycle, for instance, during the collection of products for end-of-life (EoL) treatment [23].

One of the major applications of the DPP technology is in the batteries sector. An example of a digital battery passport (DBT), a case of a DPP, is presented in Figure 3. The concept of a DBT presented hereby was developed by Berger, Schöggel and Baumgartner [27]. In this case, the DBT is a set of information that is structured into 7 levels of increasing granularity. Level 1 represents the DBT itself, while the level 2 represents the 4 main information categories included within the DBT, information on the battery itself:

- Battery identity (product number)
- Value chain actor information
- Sustainability and circularity impacts
- Diagnostics, maintenance and performance

The information contained in the DBT is then utilized in decision making process by four different stakeholders. Original equipment manufacturers can use the DBT for optimizing the environmental performance of their products throughout the entire value chain. A user of the battery can utilize the DBT to purchase a battery with the best environmental profile. Recyclers can use the DBT to access information on the battery properties, adjust their process chain and recover more materials. Lastly, regulatory bodies can utilise information embedded in DBTs to design new policy instruments and evaluate the effectiveness of the incumbent ones.

Source: Berger, K., Schöggel, J. P., & Baumgartner, R. J. (2022)

Figure 3: Visualization of the interactions with a DPP for a battery passport case; adapted from [27].

Benefits

The adoption of DPPs offers numerous benefits that align with the goals of a CE. DPPs enable circular design, as designers can use the information stored in DPPs to optimize the product design and increase the durability, repairability, reusability or energy use [28]. DPPs also enhance resource efficiency by providing detailed information on material composition and recyclability, which can lead to improved recycling rates and reduced waste. Remanufacturers benefit from the information on the disassembly and the state of health of the product components [28]. By enabling better sorting and processing of materials, DPPs can significantly contribute to the recovery of valuable resources from end-of-life products [29].

DPPs empower consumers by increasing transparency regarding the environmental impact of products, thereby fostering more sustainable purchasing decisions [30]. This consumer awareness can drive demand for circular products and encourage manufacturers to adopt more sustainable practices. Furthermore, DPPs can facilitate the development of circular business models where companies retain ownership of products and are incentivized to design for longevity and recyclability [30].

DPPs are beneficial also from the governance perspective, as they offer a robust digital solution for supply chain compliance by enabling the monitoring and reporting of key sustainability indicators such as Scope 3 greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, thereby reducing administrative burdens and facilitating long-term benefits for businesses [31]. By relying on standardized data, DPPs allow for direct comparisons of products and businesses on parameters like carbon footprint, circularity, and recycling capabilities—enhanced through blockchain certificates for low-carbon materials that underpin sustainability claims. They also address issues of confidentiality and intellectual property by implementing layered data access, ensuring that only relevant stakeholders can access sensitive information, while still offering regulators dynamic market insights to inform future policies and resolve product liability challenges [31].

2.3.1 Implementation

Data Collection layer

The data collection layer has the purpose of collecting data related to physical, technical and economic attributes of a product. When implementing the data collection layer, it is important to first identify the data needs. The data needs of a DPP vary depending on the decision-making context and the actors involved in the circular supply chain. There are 7 key data categories that are critical for a DPP [32]:

1. Data on product running hours, repair history, and external environmental conditions.
2. Serial numbers, product numbers, and country of origin.
3. Material composition, hazardous substances, and recycled content.
4. Disassembly instructions, safety guidelines, and maintenance manuals.
5. Information on suppliers, reverse logistics channels, and product return options.
6. Carbon footprint, water consumption, and other lifecycle environmental impacts.
7. Adherence to regulations like RoHS and REACH directives.

An appropriate selection of data categories is essential for supporting decision-making at various stages of the product lifecycle, from sustainable procurement to end-of-life management [27]. The identification of data needs should be a collaborative process involving multiple relevant stakeholders,

including suppliers, manufacturers, service providers, customers, and third-party recycling companies [32]. Multi-actor perspective in identifying data needs is of high importance, as the relevance, availability, and sensitivity of data vary across stakeholders [27], [33]. Each actor has distinct data requirements based on their role in the circular supply chain:

- Customers need data for sustainable procurement, product lifetime extension, and end-of-life management.
- Service Providers require data for condition-based maintenance and repair activities.
- Manufacturers rely on data to select value-retention strategies, such as remanufacturing or recycling.
- Suppliers need data on material composition and recycled content to support the use of secondary materials.
- Third-Party Recycling Companies require data on material composition and disassembly guidelines to ensure high-quality recycling.

DPP's data collection can make use of a variety of technologies, depending on the type of information collected. The data carrier is a key component of the data collection layer, linking the product to its digital information by making use of its digital identity. Information related to product characteristics such as the identity of the value chain actor handling the product or the environmental impacts associated with the product's value chain is attached to the product through its identity.

To generate an identifier unique to each product, a coding system can be used. A printing technology can be used to attach such a code to the product. In this case, the printed code can use one dimension (bar code) or 2 dimensions (QR code) to encrypt the information. Ideally, the product identifier has also a unique resource location (URL) on the internet [23]. Typically, QR codes are used, as they provide a low-cost and accessible solution for delivering basic product information. However, they have a low counterfeit resistance, which can be easily exploited [34]. Alternatively, electronic tags carrying an information can be attached to products in the form of a sticker. The electronic tags consist of small integrated circuits that are able to communicate the information in digital format to a scanner. Technologies used for this communication include NFC (near-field communication) and RFID (radio frequency identification) [35]. The advantage of the NFC/RFID data carriers is that they allow data encryption and allow contactless and automated access to data [34].

The information characterising the conditions a product is exposed to is typically collected by utilising IoT sensing technologies. For instance, smart container seals can be used to collect data related to environmental conditions [21]. Another technology that could be used is a printed sensor, which utilises functional ink. Such printed sensors can detect environmental properties, as the functional ink can react to temperature or luminosity [35]. Another technology relevant for monitoring the properties of a product in real-time is a digital twin technology [27] (as described in more detail in section 2.3).

Data curation and sharing layer

The layer of data curation and sharing is an essential building block of a DPP, as it allows the value chain stakeholders to create, modify, organize and distribute the information that constitutes a DPP. The DPP data collected is recorded to the digital storage. To enable the sharing of this data, the storage must be

accessible to all value chain actors, i.e., must be part of a network all actors have access to. A back-end system must be created. Cloud computing technology is suitable for this purpose [21]. The information can be shared within this cloud by making use of the HTTP interface.

When the information is being transferred, the security of this transmission can be ensured by the use of secure protocols. One such protocol suitable for protecting data transfer from sensors is the Datagram Transport Layer Security (DTLS) protocol [36]. DTLS can be used to build a secure point-to-point channel between the sensing device and the cloud. This technology ensures authentication of the entities with the data access, confidentiality and integration of the exchanged data. Another option for data exchange is the distributed ledger technology (DLT), which provides important data security features such as immutability and verifiability [37]. One of the DLT solutions useful to be used in the context of a DPP is IOTA Tangle [38]. The individual exchanges of data within the network are verified by the nodes that comprise the network. Within this system, the verification is incentivised by the design of the system, which requires a node to validate the two previous data exchanges in order to create a new data exchange. Another DLT-based solution for secure data sharing is Ethereum blockchain, use of which was demonstrated by Lie et al. [39].

One of the key technologies in data curation for DPPs is Big Data Analytics [21]. This technology handles the vast amounts of data generated throughout a product's lifecycle, from manufacturing to disposal. By analyzing large datasets, Big Data Analytics can provide insights into a product's environmental impact, usage patterns, and maintenance needs, which are crucial for creating a comprehensive DPP.

Machine Learning (ML) is another useful technology to be used in data curation for DPPs [21]. ML algorithms can predict and optimize various aspects of a product's lifecycle, such as maintenance schedules and recycling potential. By learning from historical data, ML models can improve the accuracy and reliability of the information included in a DPP, ensuring that stakeholders have access to up-to-date and relevant data.

The Lifecycle Information Framework Technology (LIFT) is also instrumental in data curation for DPPs [21]. LIFT enables the integration of data from various sources, creating a cohesive and accessible dataset that can be easily shared among stakeholders. This technology ensures that all relevant information about a product, from its origin to its end-of-life disposal, is captured and made available in the DPP. LIFT is essential for maintaining the digital threads that connect different data sources throughout the product lifecycle, supporting the interconnection of stakeholders and the secure collection of data [40].

Data leverage layer

Data leverage is crucial to ensure an efficient utilisation of the information contained in the DPP by all stakeholders and users. Blockchain technologies represent the most common and effective solution for data leverage [21]. Blockchain enables the decentralisation of information systems. Data stored in blockchain is distributed across multiple nodes, reducing the risk of single points of failure. This enhances reliability, especially in complex supply chains, making DPP data resilient to disruptions [41].

Blockchain has several advantageous characteristics, making it a good fit for the DPP [42]. Blockchain ensures data cannot be altered once recorded, maintaining the integrity of DPP information. This is critical for trust, as stakeholders rely on accurate data for compliance and decision-making. For example, it prevents tampering with records of material sourcing or emissions, ensuring authenticity [43]. Moreover, all transactions and data entries are visible to authorized participants, promoting collaboration across supply chains. This transparency is vital in global networks where products pass through multiple hands, ensuring all parties have access to the same information [44].

Additionally, blockchain can automate processes via smart contracts, which are self-executing agreements triggered by predefined conditions. This can streamline tasks like verifying product compliance, updating DPP data, or rewarding sustainable behaviors, reducing administrative overhead and improving efficiency [41]. Lastly, blockchain also facilitates data exchange between different systems and stakeholders, ensuring consistency and accessibility. This is particularly important for DPPs, which need to integrate with various industry standards and regulations.

Challenges

The implementation of DPPs faces several challenges that must be addressed to realize their full potential.

Several challenges related to the implementation of DPPs are of social and economic nature. The necessity of stakeholder engagement for an efficient functioning of a DPP is a considerable barrier. Indeed, all parties must recognize the value of DPPs and be willing to participate in data-sharing initiatives. This highlights a need for a common framework, which would ensure the traceability and effectiveness of DPPs in facilitating data. Without it, inefficiencies and confusion within supply chains might occur [45]. Moreover, the integration of DPPs into existing business processes requires significant investment in technology and training. Making such an investment might be a substantial barrier, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) [32].

Data access, storage and sharing are challenging the implementation of DPPs as well. Firstly, one significant hurdle is the need for standardized data formats and protocols to ensure interoperability across different systems and stakeholders [21]. Many companies already possess vast amounts of data, but it is often dispersed across different systems, making it difficult to consolidate and share [32]. Secondly, data sensitivity might restrict the data access, as certain data, such as material composition and environmental footprints, are considered sensitive and require multiple levels of access control to protect intellectual property rights. Thirdly, data storage is another challenge. Industry tends to favour avoiding the creation of one centralized, all-encompassing database. Instead, target-driven decentralized data storage strategy is seen as more viable. Hence, it is important to define the goals of a DPP early on, as they should determine the design of the system [31]. While blockchain offers many benefits for data storage, it faces challenges like high costs, integration with existing systems, and scalability issues, which could affect widespread adoption [42]. Therefore, a comprehensive plan is necessary to guide the development of a technologically sophisticated DPP system.

Success factors

To implement DPPs successfully, specific actions from various stakeholders are required in relation to the DPP data [32]. Policymakers should define mandatory data requirements while allowing flexibility for companies to protect sensitive information. The rollout of DPPs should begin on a small scale, with iterative refinements based on industrial feedback. Starting with less complex, well-defined product groups allows stakeholders to evaluate the system's impact and refine the approach before scaling it up to more complex products. Ongoing consumer research and continuous stakeholder dialogue, governed by competent institutions, are essential to adapt the DPP framework effectively over time [46]. Strong regulatory support and incentivisation is needed for a successful implementation of DPPs [47].

A careful attention should be paid to information included in a DPP. An essential technical element is the inclusion of a unique product identifier (UPI), which ensures that every component of a product—from its primary packaging to secondary packaging—is traceable [31]. For instance, a shampoo product should have traceability not only for the shampoo itself but also for the bottle and the outer packaging. This capability supports cross-sectoral applications and provides consistent, reliable data across different product layers, fostering more effective traceability throughout the value chain [46]. Ensuring collaboration among industry players is another success factor [47].

Moreover, all information included in a DPP should be verifiable against internationally recognized standards [31]. This standardization is critical to enhancing the circularity of a product's operations—from manufacturing to the end-of-life treatment of its components—ensuring that all stakeholders can trust and rely on the recorded data. Such verifiability underpins the system's integrity and facilitates sustainable practices across the supply chain. Furthermore, industrial actors should prioritize data management practices that align with CE goals. This includes digitizing manuals, improving data sharing routines, and integrating sensors to capture use-phase data.

2.3.2 Regulation specific to the DPP

The concept of DPP is particularly relevant in the context of regulatory frameworks, such as the European Commission's proposals for eco-design regulations, which advocate for the integration of DPPs to standardize product information and promote circularity [48]. By establishing a unified data structure, the DPP can facilitate better communication and collaboration among various actors in the product lifecycle, ultimately supporting the principles of a CE [30], [46].

The EU is progressively integrating DPPs into its regulatory landscape (as presented in Figure 4) as a means to enhance transparency, traceability, and sustainability in product lifecycles. DPPs are envisaged as digital records that document every stage of a product—from raw material sourcing through production, use, and end-of-life recycling—thereby supporting the EU's broader CE goals. This regulatory framework is supported by initiatives and guidelines that encourage uniform data collection and sharing across industries. DPPs are conceived as a system of potential digital solutions for CE transition and promoted as such by the European Commission in the “Circular Economy Action Plan” [31].

A cornerstone of these efforts is the EU Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) [49], which mandates that products sold within the EU meet strict environmental and energy performance criteria. The regulation entered into force in July 2024. Under this regulation, manufacturers are required to provide verifiable digital information about their products' lifecycles. The regulation postulates specific requirements for DPPs, targeting their availability, access rights and data requirements. Each DPP must be linked uniquely to a product and remain available during the expected lifetime of a product. Access to a DPP should be ensured via a UPI linked to a data carrier. The DPP should contain all mandatory data, as they are specified in the delegated acts, which will be developed for specific product groups. These delegated acts will come into force between 2026 and 2030 [50]. By implementing DPPs, companies can better demonstrate compliance with these sustainability requirements, while also ensuring that consumers have access to detailed, reliable product data. This regulation helps to minimize waste and drive the transition towards a CE [51].

In addition to the ESPR, there are sector-specific regulations that are related to DPPs. One of them, the EU Batteries Regulation [52] plays a critical role in ensuring sustainability within the battery sector. This regulation requires manufacturers to track and disclose comprehensive information regarding battery composition, recycled content, safety and storage, and removability and replaceability. This information should be all included in the battery DPP, which is often called battery passport. The creation of battery passports will become mandatory in February 2027 for all batteries larger than 2 kWh. DPPs serve as an essential tool under this framework by ensuring that all data related to battery lifecycles is accurate and easily accessible to stakeholders [34]. Such transparency not only aids in compliance but also encourages the use of more sustainable materials and processes in battery production [46].

The broader regulatory context also includes the EU Circular Economy Action Plan [53], which emphasizes the importance of sustainable production and waste reduction across all sectors. This plan advocates for the integration of digital tools—such as DPPs—to monitor product lifecycles and to foster collaboration among stakeholders throughout the value chain. By establishing common data standards and interoperable systems, the EU aims to break down silos between manufacturers, suppliers, and recyclers, ensuring that all parties are working with a consistent and verifiable set of information [54].

Overall, these individual EU regulations—the ESPR, the Battery Regulation, and the Circular Economy Action Plan—work in alignment to create a robust framework that supports the implementation of DPPs. Together, they not only mandate the collection and sharing of critical product data but also provide a clear pathway for industries to transition towards more sustainable, transparent, and circular business models.

Figure 4: Overview of the individual EU regulatory initiatives related to DPPs (source: [31]).

2.3.3 Conclusion

DPPs represent a promising innovation in advancing the CE by enabling greater transparency, traceability, and data-driven collaboration across product value chains. Through structured data collection, curation, and utilization, DPPs support informed decision-making for manufacturers, service providers, consumers, and recyclers alike. Their ability to provide detailed insights into material composition, product usage, and environmental impact enhances the implementation of sustainable practices throughout a product's lifecycle. While challenges such as data standardization, stakeholder coordination, and technological integration remain, these can be addressed through targeted regulatory frameworks, phased implementation, and industry-wide cooperation. With continued development and support, DPPs are well-positioned to become a central component of sustainable product management and circular business models.

2.4 Digital twin technology for circular battery value chain

The digital twin (DT) technology, integrated with the Internet of Things (IoT), has emerged as a transformative innovation in the realm of electric vehicle (EV) battery management. This technology creates a virtual replica of physical battery systems, leveraging advanced multi-layer models, artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), and cloud computing to enhance performance, safety, and cost-effectiveness [55]. The DT concept is not new but has evolved significantly with the advent of IoT and other digital technologies, enabling real-time monitoring and predictive analytics that were previously unattainable.

Deployment of IoT-based DT technology in EV battery management can be an important enabler of a transition to a CE. By providing a comprehensive digital representation of the battery's lifecycle, DTs facilitate better decision-making processes for repurposing and recycling. This technology orchestrates the entire battery value chain, from manufacturing to end-of-life disposal, thereby improving economic and environmental outcomes [55]. The predictive State of Health (SoH) models, a key component of DTs, enable the anticipation of battery degradation and the optimization of maintenance schedules, further contributing to CE goals by extending the useful life of batteries [55]. The utility of the DT technology for its application in the battery value chain is explored in Figure 5. The current functionalities of DTs are targeting the internal characteristics of a battery, such as state of charge (SoC) or cell voltage and temperature. These are closely related to the functions fulfilled by battery management systems (BMSs), which monitor and measure these characteristics directly based on the connection with the battery. In addition, DTs might be utilised for applications outside of the scope of battery's internal state thanks to the predictive capabilities of DT models. These applications include prediction of remaining useful life or optimization of the product design.

Figure 5: The utility of DT technology applied to batteries, adopted from [56].

The principle behind IoT-based DT technology involves creating a dynamic, real-time digital counterpart of the physical battery system, as shown in Figure 6. This digital replica is continuously updated with data from IoT sensors, allowing for accurate simulations and predictions of the battery's behaviour under various conditions. This approach is crucial for assessing the suitability of used batteries for second-life applications, such as energy storage systems, by providing detailed insights into their remaining capacity and potential degradation patterns [57]. The integration of AI and ML algorithms enables the DT to learn

from historical data and improve its predictive capabilities over time. This two-way data connectivity between the physical and DTs is crucial for the technology's effectiveness [55].

Key components

The key components of an IoT-based DT solution for EV batteries include:

- **IoT Sensors and Devices:** These are deployed on the physical battery system to collect real-time data on parameters such as voltage, current, temperature, and state of charge (SoC). The data is transmitted to the DT for processing and analysis [58].
- **Cloud Computing Platform:** The DT resides on a cloud platform that provides the necessary computational resources for data storage, processing, and advanced analytics. Cloud computing enables scalability and accessibility, allowing for real-time updates and remote monitoring [59].
- **Digital Models and Algorithms:** The DT comprises multi-scale models that simulate the battery's behaviour under different operating conditions. These models are used to predict the battery's response to various scenarios, enabling proactive maintenance and optimization strategies [58]. The DT model can be based on AI and ML as well. These algorithms can be continuously refined using ML techniques to improve accuracy and reliability [55].

Figure 6: Visualization of the data flows in a DT system; adapted from [60].

Benefits

DT technology offers numerous benefits for the repurposing of EV batteries, addressing critical challenges in battery management, performance optimization, and sustainability. The integration of DTs in

EV battery systems provides a virtual live representation of the physical battery, enabling continuous monitoring, analysis, and optimization throughout its lifecycle [55], [61].

One of the primary benefits of DT technology is the improvement in battery performance and safety. By utilizing advanced multi-layer models, AI, and cloud computing techniques, DTs can accurately predict and diagnose battery behaviour. This capability allows for the early detection of anomalies and critical failures, ensuring safer and more reliable battery operation [55], [59]. The real-time data exchange between the physical battery and its digital counterpart facilitates proactive maintenance and extends the battery's useful life [61].

Moreover, DT technology significantly enhances the cost-effectiveness of battery management. Integrating DTs can reduce costs by up to 80% and improve development efficiency by optimizing resource use and reducing the need for extensive physical prototyping [62]. The sophisticated simulation capabilities of DTs enable companies to rapidly evaluate and refine innovative solutions, shortening product development cycles and accelerating market introduction [62].

Another key benefit is the ability to predict the remaining useful life of batteries accurately. DTs can provide insights into the battery's SoH without physical inspection, allowing for better planning and scheduling of maintenance activities [59]. This predictive capability is crucial for repurposing EV batteries, as it enables the identification of batteries suitable for second-life applications, such as stationary energy storage systems [55].

DT technology also plays a vital role in advancing sustainability in the EV ecosystem. By optimizing battery performance and extending lifespan, DTs contribute to more sustainable energy storage solutions. The technology facilitates the assessment and validation of new battery cell technologies, promoting the development of high-performance and environmentally friendly batteries [62]. Additionally, DTs can help address environmental concerns by improving energy storage capabilities and reducing the carbon footprint associated with battery production and disposal [61].

2.4.1 Implementation

IoT sensors and devices

Implementing Internet of Things (IoT) technologies within DT systems necessitates addressing several critical requirements to ensure effective and efficient operation. A fundamental aspect is the establishment of a comprehensive sensor network capable of continuously collecting real-time data on battery parameters such as voltage, current, temperature, and state of charge [55]. These sensors serve as the primary data sources, feeding essential information into the DT models.

The integration of sensors like voltage dividers, current sensors (e.g., INA219), and temperature sensors enables precise monitoring of battery performance. In practice, the sensing technology can be embedded directly into the battery BMS. The integrated sensors are operated by the BMS, which carries out data collection at defined sampling rates [63]. For instance, a study developed an automated battery monitoring system utilizing IoT-based sensors to enhance operational efficiency. The system integrated a DC

voltage sensor connected to the battery and an INA219 sensor to measure current flow during battery usage, with data transmitted via the Blynk platform for real-time monitoring [64].

To ensure seamless interoperability between diverse devices and platforms, the collected data must be transmitted securely and efficiently to centralized systems for processing and analysis. This necessitates the implementation of standardized communication protocols, facilitating integration across the battery value chain. Protocols such as *Message queuing telemetry transport* (MQTT), Controlled Area Network (CAN) have been developed to address these interoperability challenges, enabling efficient and secure data exchange in IoT ecosystems [63], [65].

Cloud Platform

The cloud platform is an important component in DT systems, serving as the central hub for data integration and communication. It facilitates the seamless aggregation, processing, and dissemination of data between physical assets and their virtual counterparts. Furthermore, it provides virtually unlimited storage space, complementing the limited data storage capacity of the IoT devices. Cloud-based storage solutions such as Amazon S3 and Azure Blob Storage can be used in a DT system. They offer scalable infrastructures capable of managing extensive datasets generated by IoT devices, facilitate real-time analytics and informed decision-making processes. [66], [67]

Effective data integration within a cloud-based DT system necessitates the harmonization of heterogeneous data sources. To address this, Park et al. (2020) [68] proposed an interoperable data schema that standardizes data representation, ensuring consistency and facilitating integration across different platforms. Their cloud-based DT manufacturing system leverages this schema to enhance interoperability and data coherence.

The data transmission latency influences the efficiency of the data processing and the overall DT efficiency. Adjustments of the cloud architecture can be made to optimize this efficiency. For example, a study by Knebel et al. [69] demonstrated that integrating fog computing with cloud platforms can significantly reduce latency in DT systems, thereby enhancing real-time responsiveness. Furthermore, the integration of edge computing with cloud platforms has been explored to optimize data processing. Do-duit et al. [70] utilized edge computing to perform local data processing, reducing the computational load and data transmission delay to the cloud, which aligns with the requirements of DT systems.

DT models and Algorithms

DTs provide a virtual replica of physical batteries, enabling real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, and optimization of battery performance. Implementing a DT (DT) model involves several considerations to ensure effectiveness and reliability. The modelling of the battery dynamics can be based on three different approaches: equivalent circuit models (ECMs), electrochemical models or artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) algorithms [63]. All these models are valid and have their own limitations and advantages in modelling batteries. The choice of model depends on the specific application and requirements. ECMs are suitable for real-time applications, while electrochemical models are better for

detailed analysis. Hybrid models that combine ML with physics-based models offer a balance between accuracy and efficiency [71].

Equivalent Circuit Models (ECMs)

Equivalent circuit models abstract the electrochemical nature of batteries and represent them as electrical components. ECMs are widely used in Battery Management Systems (BMSs) due to their computational efficiency and simplicity. They typically include resistors, capacitors, and sometimes non-linear components like diodes to emulate battery behaviour [72], [73]. ECMs are straightforward to implement and require less computational power, making them suitable for real-time applications. They can accurately match battery current, voltage, and aging behaviour [73]. However, ECMs often lack precision in capturing the complex electrochemical processes within the battery. As a result, they may not accurately predict battery degradation over time [74].

Electrochemical Models

Electrochemical models provide a detailed representation of the internal processes within a battery, such as ion transport and chemical reactions. These models are crucial for understanding battery degradation mechanisms and predicting battery lifespan [73]. Electrochemical models offer high accuracy in state estimation (SoH, SoC) and can predict individual mechanisms within the battery. They are essential for control-oriented management and can enhance the monitoring and prediction of battery performance [73]. However, these models are computationally intensive and require extensive physio-chemical data. Implementing them in real-time applications can be challenging due to their complexity [75].

AI and Machine Learning Algorithms

AI and ML algorithms have emerged as powerful tools for enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of DT models. Hybrid models that combine physics-based models with ML algorithms have shown promising results in battery research [71]. ML algorithms can learn from large datasets and improve prediction accuracy over time. They can handle complex, non-linear relationships and adapt to different battery aging states. Additionally, hybrid models that integrate ML with physics-based models provide high accuracy and computational efficiency [71]. One of the disadvantages of ML models is that they require extensive training data and computational resources. The quality of predictions depends on the quality and quantity of the data used for training. Additionally, since ML models are a “black box”, they may lack interpretability, making it difficult to understand the underlying mechanisms [76].

Implementation Considerations

There are several requirements to consider when implementing a DT model. Firstly, the quality and availability of data is very important. High-quality data is crucial for training ML models. Preprocessing steps such as normalization, filtering, and feature extraction are essential to improve model performance [76]. Secondly, the computational requirements vary significantly between different models. ECMs require less computational power, while electrochemical models and ML algorithms demand more resources [74]. Thirdly, time and effort will have to be allocated for the model validation. Indeed, rigorous validation and testing are necessary to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the DT models. Comparing model predictions with real-world data is crucial for assessing performance [77].

Challenges

The implementation of DT technology for repurposing EV batteries faces several significant challenges. One of the primary obstacles is the complexity of battery systems, which involve intricate electrochemical processes and non-linear degradation patterns. Accurate state estimation, fast charging, thermal management, and extending the useful life of batteries are areas that present substantial research challenges [58]. The lack of standardization in battery recycling units further complicates the efficient tracking and tracing of battery life cycles, which is crucial for effective repurposing [78].

Moreover, the high computational requirements and the need for extensive, high-quality data pose additional hurdles. DTs rely on sophisticated algorithms and data analysis to predict battery behaviour accurately. However, developing these algorithms and ensuring data accuracy can be resource-intensive and technically demanding [55]. The integration of DTs with existing systems also requires advanced hardware and software platforms, which can be costly and complex to implement [55].

Data transmission delays and model accuracy are other critical challenges. Ensuring real-time data synchronization between the physical battery and its digital counterpart is essential for the effectiveness of DT technology. Any delays or inaccuracies in data transmission can compromise the reliability of the DT model [78].

Success Factors

Despite the aforementioned challenges, several success factors have been identified that can facilitate the implementation and replication of DT technology for EV battery repurposing.

Several factors related to the technological implementation influence the success of the potentially developed solution. One of the key success factors is the successful integration of advanced technologies such as the IoT, AI, ML, and cloud computing. These technologies enable real-time monitoring, data analysis, and predictive maintenance, which are essential for the effective operation of DTs [79]. Another critical success factor is the development of high-fidelity models that accurately replicate the behaviour of physical batteries. While it is not necessary to mirror every aspect of the original system, capturing the essential characteristics and dynamics of the battery is crucial for the reliability of the DT [56]. This requires a deep understanding of battery chemistry, degradation mechanisms, and operational conditions.

Socio-economic factors influence the viability of the DT deployment as well. Collaboration between industry stakeholders, including battery manufacturers, recycling units, and technology providers, is also vital for the successful implementation of DT technology. Establishing standardized protocols and sharing best practices can help overcome the challenges associated with data integration and system compatibility [80]. Furthermore, ensuring the economic viability of DT technology is a significant success factor. Demonstrating the cost-effectiveness of DTs in improving battery performance, extending lifespan, and reducing operational costs can drive wider adoption. This involves conducting comprehensive cost-benefit analyses and showcasing the long-term economic benefits of DT implementation [62].

2.4.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, IoT-based DT technology represents a significant advancement in the management of EV batteries, supporting the transition to a CE by optimizing repurposing and recycling processes. The integration of IoT, AI, ML, and cloud computing enables the creation of a dynamic digital replica that enhances the performance, safety, and lifecycle management of EV batteries. The implementation of DT technology for repurposing EV batteries offers significant benefits in terms of performance optimization, cost reduction, safety enhancement, and sustainability. The ability to monitor, analyse, and predict battery behaviour in real-time makes DT an invaluable tool for the future of EV battery management and repurposing. As the technology continues to evolve, its integration with advanced analytics and AI will further drive innovation and efficiency in the EV industry. However, as of now, there are several challenges faced when implementing a DT to the battery value chain. Consequently, there is no integrated tool yet that would enable prediction of the remaining battery lifetime without dismantling the given battery first.

2.5 Digital marketplace

The concept of a CE represents a transformative approach to production and consumption, aimed at minimizing waste and maximizing resource efficiency. In contrast to the traditional linear economy, which follows a "take-make-dispose" model, the CE emphasizes the continual use of resources through practices such as recycling, reusing, and remanufacturing. Digital marketplaces have emerged as pivotal enablers of this transition, providing platforms that facilitate the exchange and coordination necessary to sustain circular processes.

Digital marketplaces for CE serve as intermediaries that connect various stakeholders, including manufacturers, recyclers, and consumers. These platforms are of interest, especially for their ability to enable the exchange of information and knowledge at reduced transaction costs. Moreover, digital marketplaces enhance transparency, improve resource efficiency, and support the sharing of information across the value chain. These attributes are key, as the transition to a CE requires close coordination and exchange between stakeholders associated with various value chain steps. By leveraging digital technologies, digital marketplaces help overcome traditional barriers and factors, which hinder the uptake of the CE. These hindering factors were identified by OECD [81] and most of them can be attributed to a lack of information on supply, quality, availability, suitability, and feasibility. Subsequently, this lack leads to a (false) preference for virgin material rather than the circular alternative [82]. Additional relevant hindering factors identified by OECD are search and transaction costs, consumer perception and risk aversion, and market power [81].

The CE digital marketplace works on the principle of centralising the information on the supply and demand for waste or side streams, materials or products. In this way, it becomes the platform where the demand and the supply for individual materials can be matched and a circular flow of the materials or products established. This is typically carried out in the form of the "offer/seek" posting functionality, i.e.,

users are able to post the material or product they seek or offer and share it with other users via the centralized platform of the marketplace. Moreover, it can be a platform that facilitates safe and risk-free transactions associated with the purchase.

Key components

In technical terms, such a platform can be defined as an “extensible codebase of a software-based system that provides core functionality shared by the modules that interoperate with it and the interfaces through which they interoperate” [83]. In general, a digital marketplace for the CE can leverage various advanced technologies to facilitate the exchange of goods, services, and information among various stakeholders. The individual modules comprising the platform are determined by the platform architecture concept. Typically, marketplaces rely on a technological infrastructure composed of several key modules, each playing a critical role in ensuring seamless operation, data integrity, and user satisfaction.

Optimally, digital marketplaces can be built using a microservices architecture, which divides the application into smaller, loosely coupled services, each responsible for specific functionalities (as shown in Figure 7. This approach enhances scalability, resilience, and ease of deployment [84]. In this architecture, an API gateway serves as the single entry point for all client requests, routing them to the appropriate microservices while handling tasks like authentication, and logging [85].

Figure 7: Visualization of a microservices architecture; adapted from [86]

The user interface (UI) and user experience (UX) are crucial for ensuring accessibility and ease of use. The web design should be responsive in order to ensure that the marketplace is functional on various devices, including desktops, tablets, and smartphones. Furthermore, the flexibility of responsive design also allows for better accessibility and ease of use across different screen sizes [87]. Another design consideration to make is to use a Single Page Application (SPA) framework like React.js or Angular. These frameworks provide a dynamic and fast interface by reducing the need for full-page reloads, hence enhancing user interaction and making the use of the web application smoother. React.js, in particular,

is noted for its efficient handling of dynamic and complex UIs, making it a popular choice for modern web development [88].

Effective data management is essential for the operation of a digital marketplace. The platform typically utilizes both relational databases and NoSQL databases to store data. Relational databases like MySQL and PostgreSQL are used for structured data, while NoSQL databases such as MongoDB and Cassandra are employed for unstructured data due to their scalability and flexibility [89], [90]. Data integration is essential for data management, as it involves combining data from different sources to provide a unified view. Apache Kafka and Apache NiFi are popular tools used for managing real-time data streams and batch processing, ensuring efficient data flow and integration. These tools are vital for handling the diverse data needs of modern digital marketplaces [91].

Additional digital technologies are typically used in digital marketplaces to facilitate specific features. Firstly, a powerful search engine is vital for enhancing the user experience of the marketplace. Elasticsearch is a distributed search and analytics engine that enables quick and efficient search capabilities across large datasets [92]. Secondly, security is essential to a well-functioning digital marketplace. To ensure secure authorisation and authentication, standards like OAuth 2.0 can be used [93], while protocols such as TLS (Transport Layer Security) can be used to protect data in both transit and at rest [94].

Benefits

A digital marketplace for circular products offers numerous benefits across various stakeholders, encompassing environmental and economic advantages.

Consumers gain easy access to a wide range of circular products designed for longevity, reuse, and recycling, encouraging sustainable consumption habits. They also benefit from cost savings due to generally lower cost of recovered materials, and durability and reduced need for frequent replacements of circular products. Digital platforms often offer competitive pricing and discounts, making sustainable choices more affordable [95]. Additionally, these marketplaces provide detailed product information, certifications, and reviews, building consumer trust and ensuring that products meet sustainability standards.

Digital marketplaces facilitate the efficient use of resources by promoting the reuse, repair, and recycling of products, reducing the demand for raw materials and minimizing waste [82]. By extending the lifespan of products and finding new uses for discarded materials, these platforms help reduce waste sent to landfills, aligning with the CE's goal of minimizing waste and pollution. Furthermore, promoting the circulation of existing products lowers the overall carbon footprint associated with consumption, as the production of new products often involves significant energy consumption and GHG emissions [96].

The CE creates new job opportunities in repair, refurbishment, and recycling. Digital marketplaces facilitate the growth of these sectors, leading to economic development and likely net job creation [82]. Businesses can achieve significant cost savings by optimizing resource use and reducing waste, with digital technologies further enhancing these savings through improved operational efficiency and supply chain management [97].

2.5.1 Implementation

The implementation of a digital marketplace is a complex activity and can be generally categorized into the following steps:

1. Planning
2. Platform development
3. Launch and critical user acquisition
4. Operation

Planning and the design stage of the platform development have a determining effect on the success of the marketplace in terms of its ability to facilitate meaningful exchanges and generate profit. A well-defined, profitable business model is essential in this context. It helps in setting clear goals for the platform, guiding its functionality and circularity efforts. For instance, the platform's ability to effectively support the recovery of waste materials depends on the identification of waste streams with the highest potential for recovery. The early identification ensures that the marketplace targets the most impactful circular activities, aligning its design and operation with the most promising options for material recovery and profit generation [98]. Moreover, the development of the marketplace should account for possible errors arising from mistakes in the codebase of the platform. Hence, resources necessary for the beta-testing of the platform are required and should be accounted for when planning the development of the platform [82].

Within the functional design of the marketplace, several factors should be considered. Platforms need to prioritize simplicity and ease of use to lower entry barriers for stakeholders, including SMEs, which may have low digital readiness. This aspect is crucial for attracting and retaining users by making the platform intuitive and easy to navigate, particularly for those with limited technical skills [99]. A key challenge for SMEs in adopting digital platforms is their limited technological readiness and resources. Many SMEs struggle with adopting digital technologies, which means the platform should offer support to facilitate onboarding and use for businesses with varying levels of digital proficiency [100]. Moreover, ensuring robust security measures is critical for fostering user trust. Allocating sufficient resources to protect user data and secure transactions will help establish a legally sound and safe environment for deal-making on the platform [82]. A failure in this area can severely undermine the trust required for continued platform use. Lastly, it is important to take the user input into consideration when designing and refining the platform. In this way, the specific needs and desires of the users can be met by the marketplace operator [101].

The traditional approaches towards the digital marketplace are based on the principle of listings featuring the offered or sought material/product [82]. However, this approach does not fully address all of the informational shortcomings present among potential marketplace userbase [82]. To address all of the information hindrances, digital marketplaces should incorporate the following elements into their design [82]:

- Information on time and quantity of the supply or demand, purity (or quality) of the material, and disclosing potential additives/hazardous chemicals present in the material. Integration

with a cyber-physical system is proposed as one of the solutions. More specifically, a value-creation network between the industry, waste/side streams treatment companies and data service providers is needed.

- Algorithms dedicated to enabling automation of the markets to achieve optimal allocation of resources (in the CE). The matchmaking module is also proposed as a key element by Kosmol & Leyh [101].
- Data quality assurance through the use of standards and harmonised procedures. However, when defining the data standards, it is important to make sure that the standards do not prevent possible innovation.

Once the marketplace has been developed according to the design requirements and specifications, the operator's efforts shift primarily to ensuring a successful launch and user acquisition. The goal during this stage is acquiring the critical user mass, as will be further discussed in the section on the success factors. The operation of the marketplace then involves maintaining the existing user base, while acquiring new users, as well as iteratively refining the platform based on customer feedback.

When the marketplace is in operation and supplied with data by its users, correct data handling is essential. Indeed, the fear of data rights violation, piracy or loss of intellectual property are some of the hindrances to marketplace uptake [82]. Moreover, solid deal-making procedures are necessary to establish user trust. The following points should be ensured:

- Data protection and ensuring that the data are managed according to agreed-upon terms and that they are protected from any form of external intrusion
- Proper contract enforcement procedures to ensure legal protection of the user rights. Protection of the accounts from being hijacked or abused by an external party.
- Protection of the intellectual property rights. While detailed information (e.g., on the material composition) is essential for the optimal functioning of the marketplace, it can be very sensitive for companies to disclose. Therefore, to protect intellectual property rights, encryption and guarantee of confidentiality should be deployed.

Challenges

When implementing the circular marketplace, from the point of view of the marketplace operator, several challenges arise. The challenge most essential to the successful operation of the marketplace is the acquisition of the marketplace users. User acquisition is a key challenge, as the mass of users determines the attractiveness of the marketplace for potential users. The larger the user base, the more attractive the marketplace will be. Additionally, the platforms require a specific critical user mass in order to ensure meaningful and profitable exchanges of the materials and to create sufficient legitimacy [82]. The user acquisition is a multifaceted challenge and can be in general linked to the following issues:

- Lack of knowledge about the marketplace or own use case (knowledge to circulate own materials)
- Lack of incentive to use the marketplace. The reasons for this include low user mass which might be linked to low supply or demand of items advertised at the marketplace. Additional reason might be unsatisfactory user experience. If the platform is difficult to use, the (time) cost of adoption is

high and represents an entry barrier. The businesses might generally not be prepared for the adoption of the technology due to the low digital readiness of businesses (especially SMEs).

- Finding the right balance in the amount of information required. Too little information will be perceived as a lack of security on the quality of purchased goods. On the other hand, requiring a lot of information will result in high costs of making an offer.

Another challenge of the marketplace operation is the creation of efficient circular material flows to extract the maximum value from the side and waste streams. The marketplace should facilitate the creation of a sufficient amount of circular material flows in order to support a profitable business model. This depends on the ability of the digital marketplace to reduce the search and transaction costs and information asymmetry [82]. Also, relevant industries need to be involved with the platform to ensure that a meaningful value chain is created [82].

Success factors

User acquisition as a success factor

For the marketplace to get established among its target users, it needs to achieve a critical mass of users. This is especially important for multi-party marketplaces that need users to participate on both sides of the transaction, such as the marketplace discussed hereby. The user acquisition is primarily determined by the perceived benefits that the marketplace can provide [82]. However, the initial user acquisition process might be difficult, as the perceived benefits of the platform are influenced by the user mass, creating a negative feedback loop [82]. On the other hand, the performance of the platform is expected to improve exponentially, as the number of transactions and users grows [102].

There are several strategies that can be used to effectively reach the critical user mass and ensure a successful launch of the digital marketplace. For instance, targeted market entry can be done by identifying and focusing on niche markets with high demand [103]. Alternatively, establishing partnerships with organizations that already have a large user base can help facilitate rapid user acquisition, especially when these partnerships provide value that complements the platform's offerings [104]. Moreover, the platform can be designed to utilise network effects. Successful platforms design strategies around the network effect dynamics, ensuring that growth on one side of the marketplace attracts more users to the other side [105]. One of the ways to harness the network effect would be to subsidize the more price-sensitive side, while letting the less price-sensitive price carry the burden of this subsidy. Another way would be to provide bonuses for initial users, helping to overcome the problem of needing both sides to grow simultaneously [106].

Moreover, educating users and creating awareness about the marketplace's value proposition is essential, especially during the early stages. It helps to gain credibility and spread awareness about the benefits of the platform. Ideally, the platform would start with the potential user education even before launch. This strategy works best in sectors with high technological barriers where potential users need to understand how to interact with the platform [104]. It is essential to engage all stakeholders, especially targeting SMEs, which might be lagging in digitalization efforts. This can be done by providing specific technical know-how and support with funding [107]. Moreover, the education campaign should also address the

general lack of knowledge among the producers of waste and side streams regarding the potential value of these streams in a CE.

Establishing trust among the marketplace users is essential for acquiring new users and maintaining the existing ones by reassuring them of the marketplace's reliability. The trust can be established by the implementation of the feedback and reputation system. For instance, platforms like eBay and Uber thrive on feedback mechanisms that foster trust between buyers and sellers. By enabling users to leave ratings and reviews, platforms can mitigate transaction risks and attract more participants [108].

Addressing information asymmetry as a success factor

Mitigating the information asymmetry that exists between the seller and the buyer of the waste and side streams is crucial for efficient deal-making on the platform. It is recommended that detailed information on the material composition is provided by the sellers [82]. For instance, Migliore [109] proposed a system based on the combination of CER, NACE and Abaco codes that enables the categorization of waste streams based on their quality, quantity and source location. Thanks to a comprehensive characterization, consumer prejudice towards secondary materials can be reduced. Moreover, to reduce consumer prejudice and risk aversion, consistent data quality should be assured. This can be achieved by means of standards and defined procedures that ensure that the data collection is transparent, comprehensible and transferrable [82]. This issue is especially relevant for the case of the circular value chain creation, as the current nomenclature is often deficient in detail [82]. By providing sufficient information on the quality of the offered product, the suppliers are able to set the price according to the offered product without being affected by consumer externalities (lack of knowledge) [82]. However, it is important to take into consideration that the use of standards might have a negative effect by preventing innovation within the market due to the market lock-in [82].

On the other hand, it is important to set the required offered product information in a way that is not overwhelming for the potential sellers. While the information on the chemical composition of the offered material is desirable for the buyer, obtaining it might represent a substantial cost for the seller. The cost of obtaining detailed product information represents a barrier particularly for small businesses or SMEs with limited resources to perform such analyses.

One approach to balance this is to create standardized reporting formats that allow sellers to disclose essential but cost-effective information, reducing complexity without overwhelming them. This could include basic material properties that are easy to assess, properties required to be reported by relevant regulation, and quality certifications (associated with the process generating the waste/side streams). Moreover, leveraging digital technologies, such as Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS), could further streamline data collection by automating the tracking of materials throughout the value chain [82].

Algorithmisation and matchmaking as a success factor

Matchmaking is a service that can be provided to marketplace users to improve their experience and simplify the search for the right buyer/seller. A matchmaking feature is especially useful when the number of listings on the marketplace is high, making the search for the right match time-consuming. In general,

the matching module can be based on a database used for the matchmaking and the matchmaking algorithm. The database can be either pre-defined and managed only by the developers or also extensible by the platform users, hence leveraging the shared knowledge of the user base [101]. Moreover, the abilities of digital networks and computation can also be utilized to discover innovative solutions by recombining the existing information [82].

Łękańska-Andrinopoulou et al. [95] proposed a framework that optimizes the matchmaking process according to multiple criteria such as CE metrics or transportation-related GHG emissions. Firstly, criteria used in the framework look into the match of the companies in terms of their implementation of circular principles. Secondly, the algorithm identifies direct material flow matches (i.e., the cases when the offered waste can be directly used as a feedstock in a production process) and indirect material flow matches (i.e., the cases when a third party is needed to provide its technological capacity to process the offered waste into a form utilizable in a production process). Additionally, for each material exchange, the loop tightness, i.e., the indicator assessing the extent of value recovered from the waste, is evaluated based on the Ellen MacArthur Foundation's butterfly diagram for CE [110]. Thirdly, the GHG emissions associated with the transport between the stakeholders are assessed by considering the distance, means of transport and weight of the material. Thanks to all these features, the matchmaking module enables efficient valorisation of the waste and side streams. However, it might be good to take into consideration that matchmaking might not be very useful in the initial stages when the number of total listings is low.

2.5.2 Case Study of KiertoaSuomesta.fi

The KiertoaSuomesta.fi marketplace was first launched in Finland in 2019 by MTK - The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners. It did not reach its potential as expected. Development was started again in the TREASoURcE project in 2022 and the site was relaunched in 2023. One of the key considerations was to simplify the marketplace to make it easy to use, secure and reliable. The goal of the marketplace is to promote circulation of biobased side and waste streams by connecting producers of side streams, such as farmers, with industries that can use these resources for value-added products like biogas, biofuels, or recycled fertilizers. The marketplace serves as a hub where biobased materials can be traded, fostering both economic opportunities and sustainability.

Insights from the development and operation of the marketplace

The marketplace benefited from the close engagement with potential users, including farmers and industrial operators as the relaunched site was easier to use. Insights gained through stakeholder workshops, interviews, and user testing emphasized the need for simplicity, ease of use, and reliability. Due to the project schedule, the site had to be launched in a relatively short timeframe and user acquisition proved to be more challenging than expected. A considerable marketing budget would have been needed to reach users immediately at launch. Extensive communication efforts (onsite & online events, meetings, workshops, field days, exhibitions, social media channels, newsletters, magazine articles, website texts), have attracted more users to the site, but critical mass has not yet been reached.

The challenges regarding the marketplace cover several aspects of the value chain. The market for biobased side streams is still in its emerging stages and one of the aims of the KiertoaSuomesta.fi platform is to facilitate market development. Other challenges include logistical issues, a lack of awareness regarding utilization of the side streams, and the limited amount of the industrial users. To raise awareness about the circulation of biobased side and waste streams and about the potential of the CE, an informative section, content pages, were created to the marketplace.

Regulatory landscape

Understanding the legal aspects regulating the field, both on the handling and selling side and waste streams, but also regulations on online marketplaces, GDPR aspects, trade etc. is important. In general, all legislation affecting the sale of fertilisers is relevant, including regulations on handling and hygiene requirements for manure products (in addition to fertiliser legislation in by-product legislation). Care must be taken to ensure that the marketplace does not promote any sanction violations. It is important to follow both EU and Finnish policies to keep up to date with the changing regulatory framework. A list of the EU and national level regulations relating to KiertoaSuomesta.fi marketplace can be found in the [article](#) published in the Replication Handbook. Additionally, more information on the case of KiertoaSuomesta can be found in another Replication Handbook [article](#).

2.5.3 Conclusion

This review has explored the critical role of digital marketplaces in enabling and accelerating the transition to a CE. As a systemic alternative to the linear "take-make-dispose" model, the CE depends heavily on the exchange of information, coordination between diverse stakeholders, and efficient material flows—challenges that digital platforms are uniquely positioned to address. By centralizing information, reducing transaction costs, and enhancing transparency, digital marketplaces serve as key infrastructures that facilitate the reuse, recycling, and recovery of materials.

The analysis highlights the structural and functional elements of these platforms, from microservice-based architectures to user-centric interface design and secure data management. Furthermore, the implementation process reveals a range of technical and strategic considerations, including the need for robust business models, user acquisition strategies, and support for digitally underprepared SMEs. Particular attention was given to challenges such as information asymmetry, user onboarding, and data sensitivity—issues that must be carefully managed to build trust and ensure participation across the value chain.

In addition to addressing barriers, the study emphasizes best practices and success factors, such as standardized but flexible data reporting, matchmaking algorithms for efficient material pairing, and feedback systems to foster user confidence. These features contribute not only to platform efficacy but also to broader CE objectives, including reduced environmental impact, cost savings, innovation stimulation, and new employment opportunities.

In conclusion, digital marketplaces represent a foundational enabler of the CE, capable of mitigating existing market failures and catalyzing sustainable value creation. To realize their full potential, however, these platforms must be designed and operated with an acute understanding of the economic, technical, and behavioral dimensions of circularity. Future research should further explore more empirical case studies and develop metrics to evaluate the long-term impact of digital marketplaces on CE adoption and performance. The latter is also addressed by the work done within WP7 of the TREASoURcE project, where the sustainability effects of the deployment of a digital marketplace are studied.

2.6 Digital waste sorting system

The transition to a CE necessitates the development of efficient waste management solutions that support resource recovery and reuse. The efficiency optimization of the waste treatment processes is often halted by the heterogeneous nature of the waste streams [111]. Digital waste sorting technologies represent a key element in resolving the issues associated with the heterogeneity of waste. They have a crucial role in achieving CE goals by enhancing material sorting precision, reducing landfill waste, and increasing the availability of high-quality secondary raw materials. By integrating AI, robotics, and sensor-based technologies, digital sorting systems improve waste processing efficiency and support the transition to a sustainable, closed-loop economic model [112]. These technologies also enable the monitoring and optimization of waste flows, ensuring that valuable materials are recovered and reintegrated into the production cycle [111].

Digital waste sorting technologies leverage automation, AI, and sensor-based methods to improve the efficiency and accuracy of waste segregation. These technologies are integral to modern waste management strategies, particularly in the context of the CE, where resource optimization and material recovery are key objectives. The adoption of digitalization and robotic solutions in waste management has led to the emergence of smart bins (the smart bins technology is described in more detail in section 2.6), intelligent sorting systems, and data-driven waste tracking, all of which contribute to a more effective and sustainable approach to waste processing [111]. Moreover, ML and AI-based sorting technologies are increasingly being integrated into municipal solid waste management, as demonstrated in case studies from Xiamen, China [113], [114].

Digital waste sorting technologies support CE tasks by facilitating higher recycling rates, reducing contamination in waste streams, and enhancing the efficiency of material recovery. Sensor-based sorting and AI-driven classification help distinguish recyclable materials from non-recyclable waste, thus increasing the purity and usability of secondary raw materials. Additionally, automation in waste sorting minimizes human intervention, reducing errors and labour costs while increasing operational efficiency. These systems also contribute to better material lifecycle tracking, helping manufacturers and policymakers design more sustainable production and disposal strategies [115].

The core principle of digital waste sorting technologies is the automated identification and classification of waste materials through advanced recognition techniques. These systems utilize machine learning, AI

algorithms, and sensor-based detection to categorize waste efficiently. Commonly used techniques include Near-Infrared (NIR) Spectroscopy, X-ray fluorescence, and visual image recognition, all of which enable precise sorting of various waste materials such as plastics, metals, and paper [115]. Additionally, learning-based AI models have demonstrated high accuracy in e-waste classification, reducing sorting errors and improving recycling outcomes [116]. The technology and its components are visualised in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Visualization of the digital waste sorting system

Key components

A typical digital waste sorting system comprises several key components:

- **Sensors and Detection Devices:** These include NIR sensors, X-ray fluorescence scanners, and hyperspectral imaging cameras, which analyze the composition of waste items in real-time. These technologies enable precise material classification, reducing sorting errors and ensuring better recycling outcomes [115].
- **AI and ML Algorithms:** These are employed to classify waste based on pre-trained models, improving sorting accuracy and enabling adaptation to different waste streams. AI-based systems continuously learn from new data, refining their classification capabilities over time [115]. For instance, AI-driven classification models have been employed for sorting COVID-related medical waste, ensuring safer and more efficient waste handling [117].
- **Robotic Sorting Arms:** Robotic systems equipped with precision grippers sort waste items at high speeds, significantly enhancing sorting efficiency. These robotic systems are particularly effective in handling mixed waste streams, increasing throughput and reducing labor dependency [111].

- **Data Management Systems:** Integrated software solutions monitor waste flow, track recycling rates, and optimize sorting parameters based on real-time data. These systems provide valuable insights for policymakers and industry stakeholders, enabling data-driven decision-making to enhance waste recovery efforts [113].

These components collectively enable the automation of waste sorting, improving efficiency, reducing costs, and supporting the broader goals of CE strategies. The continuous advancement of these technologies promises further improvements in waste sorting capabilities, making them an essential component of sustainable waste management.

Benefits

Implementing a digital waste sorting system offers numerous benefits that can significantly enhance waste management practices. One of the primary advantages is the improvement in sorting accuracy and efficiency. Digital sorting systems, often powered by AI and ML algorithms, can identify and categorize waste materials with high precision, reducing the likelihood of contamination and ensuring that recyclable materials are correctly processed. These systems have demonstrated the ability to achieve very high purity levels of 97-99% in specific applications [118], [119].

Another key benefit is the reduction in operational costs. Automated sorting systems can handle large volumes of waste more efficiently than manual sorting, leading to significant cost savings. These systems can operate continuously, minimizing the need for labor-intensive processes and reducing the associated costs [120].

Moreover, digital waste sorting systems can enhance data management and tracking. These systems can collect and analyze data on waste generation, composition, and disposal patterns, providing valuable insights for waste management strategies. This data can be used to optimize waste collection routes, predict waste generation trends, and improve overall waste management efficiency [120].

Digital waste sorting systems also contribute to environmental sustainability. By improving the sorting process, these systems help recover valuable materials that can be recycled or upcycled, reducing the amount of waste sent to landfills and the amount of the primary materials that need to be produced. This not only conserves natural resources but also reduces environmental impacts associated with waste landfilling [121].

2.6.1 Implementation of Digital Waste Sorting Systems

Sensors for Waste Identification

Sensors play a crucial role in digital waste sorting by enabling real-time identification and classification of materials. The overview of different sensing technologies that can be used for the waste recognition is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of the sensing technologies used in digital waste sorting systems [111].

Sensed property	Separation criteria	Scope of application
Visible light	Colour	Glass, Paper-Cardboard-Cardboard Packaging, Plastics, Metals
Near-infrared	Chemical composition	Paper-Cardboard-Cardboard Packaging, Plastics, Wood; problematic for black plastics
transmission	Density	Plastics, Metals, Inert fraction, from construction sites, Wood
fluorescence	Elemental composition	Metals, Plastics (halogen-containing, such as PVC)
-infrared	Chemical composition	Black Plastics
Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy	Chemical composition	Aluminium-alloys, Plastics, Wood

Optical Sensors: These sensors use visible light to distinguish colors and textures, aiding in differentiating between paper, plastics, and metals. They are widely used in automated sorting systems where color-coding plays a significant role in material classification [122].

Infrared Spectroscopy: This technology utilizes the infrared radiation to detect the chemical composition of materials, making it particularly effective for sorting different types of plastics. Near-infrared (NIR) is commonly used in waste sorting facilities to identify polymer types, though it struggles with black plastics due to their low reflectivity [123].

X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) and X-ray Transmission (XRT) Sensors: These sensors identify the elemental composition and density of waste materials. XRF is particularly useful for detecting hazardous metals and differentiating plastics like PVC, while XRT helps separate materials based on density, such as metals from plastics and inert fractions from construction waste [124], [125].

Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS): This emerging technology offers rapid chemical analysis and is particularly useful for sorting complex waste streams such as aluminium alloys, plastics, and wood. It provides detailed information on the elemental composition of the material streams, enabling a targeted material recovery [126].

As not all sensors detect the same property of the material flows, a combination of several sensors helps increase the dimensions of collected information. Indeed, there is a current trend of integrating multiple sensors of various types [127]. In this way, it enhances the overall sorting accuracy. For example, optical sensors can be used in conjunction with near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy to improve the identification of contaminants and ensure higher purity of the sorted materials. This combined approach helps mitigate the limitations of individual sensing methods, such as the challenges faced by optical sensors in identifying dark or dirty materials [128].

AI and Algorithm Integration

Selection of the AI model

The choice of the AI model is crucial for the effectiveness of the waste sorting system. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are particularly well-suited for this task due to their ability to process and analyze visual data. For instance, the Inception-v3 model, a deep learning architecture based on CNNs, has shown high accuracy in waste sorting tasks. This model can be trained to recognize various types of waste materials based on their visual characteristics, such as shape, color, and texture [128].

Additionally, transfer learning techniques can be employed to leverage pre-trained models like ImageNet, which can be fine-tuned for specific waste classification tasks. This approach reduces the need for extensive data labelling and accelerates the training process [129]. Additionally, ResNet, MobileNet and YOLOv5 algorithms were found to increase the waste recognition to 98% [130].

Training the Model

Training the AI model involves feeding it a large dataset of labelled waste images. The dataset should be diverse and representative of the types of waste the system will encounter. This includes variations in material composition, size, cleanliness, and appearance. The model learns to identify and classify waste items by analyzing these images and extracting relevant features. For example, a study proposed a smart plastic waste separation system that utilized sensors and deep learning algorithms [128]. The system was trained using a combination of near-infrared (NIR) sensors, humidity sensors, temperature sensors, CO₂ sensors, CH₄ sensors, and a laser profile sensor, along with an RGB camera. This multi-sensor approach enhanced the model's ability to accurately classify waste materials based on their composition and appearance.

Sorting Parameters

The sorting parameters are critical for the system's performance. These parameters include the types of waste materials to be sorted, the desired purity levels, and the sorting speed. The AI model should be configured to optimize these parameters based on the specific requirements of the waste management facility. For example, such a hierarchical deep learning method was proposed for sorting and identifying waste in food trays [131]. This method classified waste into multiple categories based on material or shape, using faster regions with convolutional neural network features. The system was designed to handle complex waste streams and achieve high accuracy in sorting tasks.

Continuous Improvement

The implementation of AI in waste sorting systems is an iterative process. Continuous monitoring and evaluation of the system's performance are essential to identify areas for improvement. The model should be regularly updated with new data to enhance its accuracy and adapt to changes in waste composition. For instance, the integration of AI with the IoT can provide real-time data monitoring and control, enabling dynamic adjustments to the sorting process. This approach ensures that the system remains efficient and effective over time [132].

In conclusion, the implementation of AI and deep learning algorithms in digital waste sorting systems involves a careful selection of models, rigorous training processes, thoughtful operational considerations,

and continuous optimization of sorting parameters. This integrated approach enhances the efficiency and accuracy of waste management, contributing to a more sustainable and CE [120].

Robotic Sorting Arms

Features of a Robotic Arm in Waste Sorting

Robotic arms in waste sorting are equipped with advanced vision systems, typically using high-resolution cameras and sensors. These systems enable the robot to identify and classify different types of waste materials based on their visual characteristics, such as shape, color, and texture. For instance, AI-driven computer vision systems can recognize materials across various classes, differentiating between packaging and non-packaging materials, and even between food and non-food grades [133].

The precision of the sorting can be optimized by the design of the robotic arm. The choice of gripper is crucial for the effectiveness of the sorting process. Grippers must be versatile and robust to handle a wide range of materials, including plastics, metals, paper, and organic waste. Advanced grippers can be designed with adaptive features to manage different shapes and sizes of waste items, ensuring precise and efficient sorting [134].

These robotic systems leverage multiple actuation mechanisms, including vacuum suction, grippers, and magnetic attachments, to handle various types of waste. For example, vacuum suction technology is highly effective for picking lightweight materials such as plastic and paper, whereas magnetic sorting arms are used to extract ferrous metals from mixed waste streams [135]. Some advanced robotic sorting systems, such as Pick-and-Toss mechanisms, have been introduced to accelerate sorting speed by replacing the traditional Pick-and-Place approach [136].

Integrating AI and machine learning algorithms enhances the robotic arm's ability to make real-time decisions and improve sorting accuracy. These algorithms can be trained on large datasets of waste images to recognize and classify materials accurately. For example, deep learning models like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are commonly used to process visual data and improve the robot's sorting capabilities [118].

The complexity of the waste stream is a critical factor to consider when implementing robotic sorting arms. Heterogeneous waste streams, such as municipal solid waste, pose significant challenges for robotic systems. The robot must be capable of handling a wide variety of materials and adapting to changes in the waste stream's composition [137]. Furthermore, the sorting speed and throughput of the robotic system are essential for maintaining efficiency in waste management facilities. Robotic arms must operate at high speeds to keep up with the incoming waste stream while maintaining accuracy. For instance, AI-powered robotic systems can achieve an average of 55 picks per minute, significantly enhancing productivity [118].

Data Management Layer

The implementation of a digital waste sorting system involves creation of an efficient data management layer to monitor, analyze, and optimize waste flow and recycling rates. It is essential to establish a robust

data infrastructure that can handle the vast amounts of data generated by IoT sensors and other sources. This infrastructure should include scalable data storage solutions, such as cloud-based databases, and efficient data processing systems that can analyze and interpret the data in real-time [138].

Another component of the data management layer is integrated data generation technology, such as IoT sensors and DTs. DTs in this case create virtual representations of waste sorting facilities, allowing operators to simulate different process configurations before implementing them in real-world settings. This technology enables real-time optimization and predictive maintenance by integrating IoT sensors that provide data on equipment performance, waste composition, and sorting efficiency [139]. By leveraging DTs, operators can detect potential equipment failures, reduce downtime, and optimize sorting parameters to enhance overall sorting system performance.

Challenges

Despite the potential benefits, several challenges hinder the widespread adoption of digital waste sorting technology.

Firstly, the cost of AI-driven waste sorting systems, including sensors, robotic arms, and data infrastructure, remains a significant barrier [120]. While the initial investment can be high, the long-term benefits, such as reduced labor costs and improved efficiency, often outweigh the upfront expenses [120].

Secondly, the complexity of waste streams also poses a significant challenge [140]. Waste materials vary greatly in composition, size, and type, making it difficult to design sorting systems that can handle all types of waste efficiently. For example, plastics need to be separated by type and color before reprocessing, which adds to the complexity of the sorting process [141].

Thirdly, AI models require extensive training datasets, and poor-quality data can reduce classification accuracy. Additionally, the lack of uniform waste classification standards can complicate AI training and interoperability between different sorting systems [120].

Success factors

To successfully implement digital waste sorting systems, several key factors must be considered. Investment in advanced sorting technologies is a crucial enabler. While the initial investment is high, the digital sorting technology can significantly improve the efficiency and accuracy of waste sorting, making the whole sorting process more cost-efficient [120]. When calculating the cost-efficiency, the essential factors to consider are the cost of integration into existing waste management infrastructure and the economic value of the waste fractions separated after sorting [141]. Additionally, the cost-efficiency should be prioritized during the system design. One of the solutions for the cost-efficient deployment of AI algorithms and managing computational demands are cloud-computing and edge-computing technologies [142].

Collaboration between stakeholders, including waste management companies, technology providers, and policymakers, is another critical success factor. Establishing partnerships can facilitate the sharing of best practices, resources, and innovative solutions. This collaborative approach can help overcome

the challenges associated with implementing digital waste sorting systems and ensure their long-term sustainability [120].

Lastly, adaptability and scalability are essential for replicating waste sorting systems in different regions. The systems must be flexible enough to accommodate variations in waste composition and local regulations. Scalable solutions should be tailored to meet the specific needs of different communities, ensuring that the benefits of digital waste sorting are realized on a broader scale in various regions [143].

2.6.2 Conclusion

The transition to a CE relies heavily on innovative technologies that can address the challenges posed by complex and heterogeneous waste streams. Digital waste sorting technologies—integrating artificial intelligence (AI), advanced sensor systems, robotics, and data management infrastructure—offer a transformative solution for optimizing resource recovery and minimizing landfill dependency. These systems significantly enhance sorting precision, operational efficiency, and data-driven decision-making, all of which are crucial for supporting CE goals.

Despite challenges such as high implementation costs, technological complexity, and the need for high-quality training data, digital sorting systems have demonstrated substantial benefits. These include improved material purity, reduced operational costs, and enhanced environmental sustainability. With strategic investments, stakeholder collaboration, and a focus on adaptability and scalability, digital waste sorting technologies have the potential to revolutionize waste management practices across various regions.

2.7 Sensor-based systems to aid the collection of waste

Collection of municipal waste is a resource-intensive task associated with considerable costs and environmental impacts. However, collection routes created by drivers are often not efficient, as they often lack a sound informational base and do not consider the waste fill level of the waste bins. This leads to unnecessary costs and environmental pollution caused by inefficient routing and scheduling of the waste collection [144]. Difficulties related to the informational needs arising during the waste collection can be classified as the need for better routing and scheduling, i.e., the need to plan the waste collection route scheduled at a specific time [145]. Essentially, the waste collection optimization represents a reverse logistics problem, i.e., multiple collection points need to be connected to a single delivery point with minimized fuel consumption [146]. Therefore, a solution that provides an evidence-based approach to optimize the waste collection routing is needed.

To tackle the problem of the optimization of waste collection, systems of varying complexity consisting of sensors, IoT technology and algorithmic route optimization have been proposed. Most of the solutions proposed in the literature focus on the deployment of smart bins with sensors that allow monitoring of the

waste level rather than computational optimization of the waste collection route and its schedule [147]. The main purpose of such systems is to provide waste management companies and consumers with the technology to monitor the real-time waste fill levels inside waste bins. For instance, a system for real-time solid waste bin monitoring was proposed by Mamun et al. to be deployed in Malaysia [148]. Furthermore, a system for notifying users when the container waste level exceeds a specific threshold and the container needs to be emptied was proposed by Rahman et al. [132]. However, while these systems allowed for sensor-informed collection of waste based on the waste fill level, the optimization of the collection route was not addressed.

On the other hand, multiple systems with algorithmic optimization of the waste collection routing were proposed and deployed. For instance, a system for waste-level monitoring and optimization of the route for the collection of the containers that are full was proposed by Singh et al. [145]. Moreover, also more advanced optimization approaches that consider real-time status of the waste bins, load of the collection vehicle, conditions of the road and other parameters have been proposed. For instance, Priyadarshi et al. [147] proposed a holistic framework for smart solid waste collection that uses dynamically changing real-time data from the smart bins during the collection optimization. Similarly, Akhtar et al. have implemented the algorithmic optimization of the waste collection routing coupled with the data from smart bins in Malaysia [149]. In addition, Moni et al. [150] proposed a smart container system consisting of ultrasonic sensors connected to the information system via IoT technology and providing data for the collection route optimization by using the Travelling Salesman algorithm.

The key components of the sensor-based system for the optimization of waste collection, as illustrated in *Figure 9*, consists of the following components:

- Sensors
- Communication technology
- Optimization algorithms

Figure 9: Visualization of the waste collection optimization system; adapted from [151].

2.7.1 Benefits

The waste collection route optimization systems that make use of computational optimization approaches were reported to improve the efficiency of the waste collection significantly. For instance, the solution proposed by Singh et al. was found to decrease the distance travelled during the waste collection by up to 45% [147]. Similarly, it was found that the solution proposed by Akhtar et al. resulted in the increase of the waste collection efficiency by 37.6%, while leading to the decrease of the fuel consumption, fuel-related costs and CO₂ emissions by 50%, 47.8%, and 44.7%, respectively [149]. In addition, a solution proposed by Jovičić et al. [152] was reported to have a potential to reduce the distance travelled by 28.1%, while reducing the associated CO₂ emissions by 40%.

2.7.2 Implementation

The implementation of the system is discussed for each of the subsystems comprising the sensor system as such. These subsystems are sensors, integration network and algorithm computing. In general, the implementation of the sensor system consists of the following steps:

1. Planning and procurement
2. Installation
3. Operation

Planning and procurement have an essential role in the effectiveness of the implementation of the sensor system, as the system design determines the potential system performance. The guidance for the implementation of the three parts of the system is provided in the subsequent subsections.

Sensors

Sensors can be deployed in waste bins to acquire several types of information about the waste bins: waste fill level, weight of the waste inside the bins, temperature, humidity or gas composition inside the bin. The informational requirements for the proposed system involve data on waste fill level and also the weight of the waste (for a more advanced optimization). The most commonly used sensors for monitoring of the waste fill level inside the waste bins are ultrasonic and infrared light sensors.

The following factors should be taken into account when procuring sensors:

- *Sensor detection range*: its ability to detect distance within a specific range. Ideally, the sensor range should exceed or equal the depth of the container.
- *Resolution*: the smallest change in the distance of the object that the sensor is able to distinguish. The lower the resolution, the more precise the waste fill level measurements and also the optimized waste collection routing will be.
- *Ability of the sensor to reduce the interfering influence of the conditions of an environment*.
- *Ability of the sensor to filter the noise caused by uneven surfaces*.
- *Cost*.

Ultrasonic sensors

The distance sensing by ultrasonic sensors is based on the time of the flight of the ultrasonic pulse, i.e., the time it takes the ultrasonic pulse to be released, reflected back by the sensed surface and received by the sensor [153]. The ultrasonic sensors are typically installed at the top of the container [148].

XL-MaxSonar-WRA1 [154] was used by Mamun et al. [153]. This sensor has low energy consumption, is weather resistant, has a resolution of 1 cm, detection range of more than 7 m and calibrates automatically to the changes in the external conditions (ambient noise or humidity). The sensor also has a built-in firmware that allows filtering of the noise from smaller objects and detection of the noise from the largest acoustic surface. This feature is important for the application in the waste bins, as the irregular surface of the solid municipal waste might cause erroneous waste fill level detection. The researchers found that the waste fill level results produced by this sensor were burdened with an error of 5-10%. Moreover, the magnitude of the error was found to be inversely proportional to the waste fill level and sensor was assessed to be appropriate for the application in a waste bin [153].

An ultrasonic sensor model that is commonly in waste bins is HC-SR04. In one of its application cases, several ultrasonic sensors were installed at different heights to monitor waste fill level inside a roll-on/roll-off container [155]. On the other hand, the sensor can be also used in a singular way, being directed perpendicularly towards the bottom of the container [156]. The advantage of this sensor is its low cost, but it does not feature signal filter to reduce the erroneous results due to uneven surfaces of reflection and also does not calibrate based on changing external conditions [157]. The sensor has to be connected to a microcontroller such as Arduino or Raspberry Pi, where also signal filtering can be incorporated in

the signal processing process. The resolution of this sensor was found to be 7 cm [158], which will lead to less precise results compared with sensors with higher resolution. The range of the sensor is 2 to 400 cm [157].

Infrared light sensors

The infrared light sensors are based on detecting the change between emitted and received infrared radiation. They operate with the light wavelengths in the range of 0.75 to 1000 μm . However, the infrared sensors cannot directly sense the distance of the detected object without having sufficient information about the surface of the object [159]. This means that in their application in waste bins (where waste placed inside the container has unknown surface properties), they can only provide information on whether there is an obstacle in the way of the light beam. Therefore, to use infrared light sensors for waste fill level measurement, it is necessary to make use of several sensors installed at different heights corresponding to differing waste fill levels. In this setting, the axis of the sensors is parallel with the bottom of the waste bin.

Such a sensor system was proposed by Singh et al., who placed infrared light sensors at different height levels of the container. In their system, once the waste level reaches the height of the sensor, a change in the infrared radiation is detected by the sensor and the information of the waste level is updated [145]. Premgi et al. [160] utilised infrared light sensors to create a mesh of the infrared light beams between emitters and receivers to measure uneven surfaces of waste inside the bin more accurately. The researchers used linear algebra to calculate the ideal positioning of the emitters and receivers in order to create a 3D image of the waste placed inside the bin with a desired resolution. In this system, the sensors were installed at three heights to determine whether the waste fill level within a given section of the bin is in one of the 4 levels: < 25%, < 50%, < 75%, and > 75%.

Comparison of infrared and ultrasonic sensors

There are several important differences between ultrasonic and infrared sensors. The most important difference is the ability of ultrasonic sensors to sense the fill level directly. On the other hand, for infrared light sensors to be used for a distance measurement, the surface properties of the object reflecting the radiation must be known prior to the measurement [159], which is not possible for the application in the waste bins. Therefore, several infrared sensors have to be installed at varying heights of the waste bin for the measurement of its waste fill level. In general, infrared light sensors provide faster response time compared with ultrasonic sensors [159]. The ultrasound sensors are considered to perform poorly in terms of angular resolution and can only accurately detect objects that are almost normal to the sensor's acoustic axis [159].

Compared with the ultrasonic sensors, the infrared sensors do not require the bin/container to be closed by a lid [159]. Cost-wise, infrared light sensors are the more cost-efficient option [159]. Indeed, ultrasonic sensor systems were reported to be about twice as expensive as a corresponding system based on infrared sensors [160]. However, low-cost ultrasonic sensors are available on the market. It was proposed that ultrasound and infrared sensors could be used together in a complimentary way to increase the accuracy of the distance sensing. More specifically, ultrasound sensors are proposed to be used initially

to measure the distance and calculate the surface properties, which are then used when processing signal from the infrared sensor [159].

Other sensors

In addition to measuring the waste fill level of the container, sensors can be used to provide information about numerous parameters of the waste bin. For instance, information about the weight of the waste inside the bin can be measured by load sensors and used in the waste collection route optimization. Furthermore, information on the type of material placed inside the waste bin can be acquired by capacitive and inductive proximity sensors and used to improve sorting of the waste. In addition, sensors measuring temperature, humidity and chemical composition of the gas phase inside the bin can be used to monitor decomposition and prevent accidents.

Capacitive proximity sensors

Capacitive proximity sensor operates on the principle of measuring of the dielectric constant of an object located in the electromagnetic field of the sensor. In this way, it allows identification of different types of materials based on their relative permittivity (dielectric constant), e.g., paper, metal or glass can be identified. This sensor can be used to identify the type of waste placed into a waste bin [161]. Ahmad et al. [162] have demonstrated the use of capacitive proximity sensors in detecting the waste placed on a conveyor belt. More specifically, the sensors were able to distinguish between different types of paper and plastic and their combinations. However, several parameters affect the ability of the system to identify the materials accurately. For the detection of metallic materials, an inductive proximity sensor might be more useful. This sensor detects the objects that cause a change in the induced electromagnetic field [161].

Load sensors

Load sensors (also called Load Cells) are used to measure the weight of the waste inside the container. They are installed at the bottom of the container [148]. Measurement of the weight is based on the resistance change of a conductor, length of which changes, as it is exposed to changing pressure caused by the change of the load within the bin [153]. For instance, Wheatstone Bridge Network is a load sensor system built of at least four strain gauges with four separate resistors that can sense the change of load [153]. The information obtained from the load sensors allows incorporating the weight of the waste collected by individual vehicles in the collection route optimization model. For example, load sensor information was used to calculate the real-time capacity of the individual waste collection vehicles in the optimization model proposed by Akhtar et al. [149].

Temperature and humidity sensors

These sensors are installed at the top of the container to measure the temperature and humidity inside the container [148].

Ethanol gas sensors

Ethanol sensor can be very useful in monitoring the decomposition processes as ethanol was found to be the main component of the decomposition gases of the municipal solid waste [163]. MQ-3 ethanol gas

sensor was used to monitor the concentration of ethanol inside the container, indicating the degree of the decomposition of the waste [155].

Integration into the system through IoT

To establish an IoT system, it is necessary to enable a connection of the sensors with a central node, at which the data get processed and utilized to inform actions such as the waste collection routing. The sensors are typically integrated into the IoT system by being connected to a microcontroller equipped with a wireless communication module. In general, several wireless communication protocols can be used, such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, GPRS or ZigBee.

Microcontroller

Arduino is a commonly used microcontroller that supplies the sensors with power, receives and processes the signal from the sensors and communicates this information to a central point, such as server. The Arduino microcontroller can be powered by three 1.5V batteries and represents a low-cost option. Moreover, there are many libraries developed for Arduino, which simplify its use with sensors. For instance, Arduino IR library can be used to connect IR sensors with Arduino board seamlessly [160]. Another low-cost microcontroller option is Raspberry Pi Pico, which is available at \$4 [164]. Another option, if more advanced computing would be required, is to use a single-board computer, such as the Raspberry Pi 2, which was used by Singh et al. [145] and is available at a relatively low cost (around 40€ [165]).

Communication technology: Wi-Fi

Wi-Fi is a commonly used communication protocol for IoT application. Its transmission range and rate, acceptable power consumption and cheap cost are factors that make it an ideal choice for IoT applications [166]. For its application in the waste bin sensor system, the local Wi-Fi networks prevalent in urban areas can be used to enable the connection of the microcontroller to the cloud server via the internet [167]. For instance, ESP8266 ESP-01, also known as Wi-Fi module, was connected to an Arduino microcontroller and used for wireless communication between the sensors and a website that processed the sensor-collected data [155]. The ESP8266 module is commonly used in the smart waste bin applications, as it is very cost-efficient. In some systems, Wi-Fi module was also combined with other wireless communication modules. For example, Raspberry Pi 2 board could be fitted with the WiFi and GSM modules [145] to allow connection to the internet even in the case when local Wi-Fi network would not be available. Wi-Fi is particularly suitable for the use in densely-populated urban areas, where frequent updates on the waste fill level status are necessary. On the other hand, it is less suitable for an application in rural areas due to lower Wi-Fi coverage [155].

Communication technology: GSM/GPRS

Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM) and General Packet Radio Service (GPRS) are protocols of the second generation of the cellular communication network (2G). These protocols can be used to communicate the data detected by sensors via a mobile network and also facilitate the connection to the internet [168]. GSM SIM 900a modem (which can be easily connected to a microcontroller) is a common choice to facilitate the communication between the microcontroller and a remote server. The modem was used to communicate with the server using a GSM/GPRS connection [161]. In another sensor

system, GPRS protocol was used to communicate the information between the gateway that receives data from the sensors and stores them locally and the central server [148].

Communication technology: ZigBee

One of the wireless communication protocols used for sensor systems is ZigBee. This protocol is designed for low data rate, low energy consumption and close proximity. The defined rate is up to 250kbit/s. Due to its low energy consumption, the range of the signal transmission is only up to 100 meters [169]. Therefore, for the application in waste bin sensor system, a local node (gateway) collecting information from sensors connected through ZigBee and transmitting it over longer distances via another protocol is necessary. Such a system was established by Mamun et al. who proposed a system with ZigBee protocol being used for communication between sensor and a gateway and GPRS protocol was used for the communication between the gateway and a central server [148]).

Waste collection route optimization

To utilize the collected sensor data efficiently, for a waste collection route optimization, specific computational approaches were proposed. The problem of optimizing the waste collection routing has been tackled using a model of the capacitated vehicle routing problem, i.e., the problem of finding an optimal route between the depot and several locations, in which the vehicles have a constrained capacity [149]. The problem can be considered an NP (non-deterministic polynomial)¹ problem [146], i.e., finding the optimal solution requires a substantial computational effort.

Meta-heuristic approaches

Meta-heuristic approaches have been proposed to reduce the computational time and provide shortened routing even though the found solution is not guaranteed to be optimal [146], [149]. More specifically, genetic algorithms, tabu search and variable neighbourhood search algorithms were proposed to solve the problem [146]. For instance, a backtracking search algorithm was used and showed the ability to provide significant improvements in the solid waste collection [149]. In addition, a k-top cluster algorithm was used by Mirchandani et al. to solve the optimization problem [170].

Non-heuristic approaches

However, also conventional mathematical approaches, such as linear programming have been successfully used to solve the waste collection vehicle routing problem [147]. Nevertheless, it is important to note that the use of these conventional algorithmic approaches might be faced with limitations, as they are less effective for large-scale problems [149].

For example, Priyadarshi et al. [147] used agent-based modelling approach to solve the routing problem based on the temporarily varying waste level in the waste bins in the system. In their approach, the waste

¹ Non-deterministic polynomial problems cannot be solved in polynomial time (i.e., the time needed to solve the problem is a polynomial function of the size of the input to the algorithm, for instance, the amount of the collection points and size of the vehicle fleet) and require a bigger computational effort and time.

collection vehicles represented the agents with attributes of distance travelled and waste fill percentage. The environment in the agent-based model was comprised by the road network, bins and depot, and characterized by the route length, distance and waste fill percentage of the bins. The model was designed to update the routing optimization based on real-time data from the bins. The objective of the optimization was to find the minimum distance during the waste collection while maximising the amount of waste collected. Mixed integer linear programming was used to solve the waste collection routing problem, with the use of Gurobi optimizer, solving the problem in polynomial time [171]. The solution was implemented at Chandigarh, India and found to decrease the distance travelled during the waste collection by up to 45%.

A different approach towards optimization was chosen by Baby et al. [172] who proposed to use machine learning to generate predictions of container filling to inform the route optimization.

The use of geographic information systems

Geographic information system (GIS) technology plays an important role in the route optimization effort. The existing GIS databases are an important source of data for the optimization, e.g., Open Street Map database provides data on the road network [147]. Furthermore, the use of ArcGIS software package in the routing optimization allows to take the road conditions, e.g., traffic density, into consideration during the optimization process [149], [173]. ArcGIS Network Analysis Tool was also used by researchers to solve the vehicle routing problem and applied on a case study in Serbia [152]. It yielded good results, as it was found that this implementation could reduce the distance travelled by 28.1%, while reducing the CO₂ emissions by 40%. Moreover, it was pointed out that the representation of the collection area in three dimensions is beneficial for further efficiency improvements, especially in areas with significantly hilly terrain [174]. Furthermore, it was shown that the optimization effort should be focused primarily on the fuel consumption rather than just finding the shortest path, as the slope of the road is an important factor to consider [33].

Factors to consider in the route optimization design

Firstly, the more advanced the optimization model is, the bigger the potential improvement achieved by the optimization. The important elements that should ideally be included in the optimization model include the *Real-time capacity of the waste collection vehicles*, *Real-time status of the waste fill level*, *3D surface of the waste collection area* and *Information on the road conditions and traffic patterns*. Furthermore, the optimization models might determine the time for waste collection with a differing degree of complexity. A simpler approach is to determine a threshold waste level, i.e., a value of the waste fill level at which the waste bin should be considered for collection. The threshold waste level of 75% has been used by Moni et al. [150] and Akhtar et al. [149]. On the other hand, *SmartPlans* technology by *Enevo* represents a more advanced approach, with dynamically changing waste fill level projections up to 4 weeks into the future being used for route optimization [175].

Secondly, the selection of the parameters of the system to be optimized is important. Ideally, the parameter optimized by the algorithm should be identical with the parameter that the stakeholders want to optimize. For instance, selecting fuel consumption as a parameter to optimize rather than just choosing the

distance travelled by vehicles. Indeed, Tavares et al. found that the optimization effort should be focused primarily on the fuel consumption rather than just finding the shortest path, as the slope of the road is an important factor to consider [174].

Thirdly, the number of the bins that the collection route is optimized for is an important factor that influences the degree of improvement. In general, the more bins are considered for the optimization, the higher the potential optimization benefit can be, as has also been found by Omara et al. [151], who applied the examined heuristic approaches to the waste collection optimization.

Challenges

One of the challenges associated with the operation of sensor systems is the need for a power supply in locations where there is no easy connection to the electricity grid. This challenge is typically tackled by powering the system with batteries. Ideally, the least energy-consuming technology should be used, as it could be battery-powered without a need for frequent exchange. For instance, a commercially available ultrasonic sensor by *Enevo* is powered by a 3.6V Lithium battery, which is estimated to have a lifespan of more than 10 years [175]. The need for reduced energy consumption was addressed by using a system that integrates an accelerometer mounted on the lid of the bin. This design allows the other sensors than the accelerometer to be in a sleeping mode until the lid is opened and closed, with the measurement being done subsequently and the sensors turning into sleeping mode again. In specific, the LIS331DLH motion sensor was used by the researchers [153]. On the other hand, Nagarathna addressed the challenge of the power supply proposing a sensor system that involves a solar panel that supplies the power to sensors and microprocessor [176].

Success factors

For the successful implementation of an IoT-based waste collection system, several factors are critical. Firstly, the architecture and scale of the system are of utmost importance, as dense networks of sensors enable greater cost reductions and efficiency. For example, larger numbers of nodes in sensor networks increase the system's ability to optimize routes and minimize energy consumption, especially in dynamic and large-scale setups [177]. Secondly, the representation of reality in the model is crucial; more accurate models of the real-world waste management scenario allow for better route optimization and cost efficiency. For instance, real-time bin status updates integrated into optimization models can significantly reduce operational costs while improving waste collection efficiency [178]. Finally, real-time data collection and prospective route optimization are essential for improving precision. Systems equipped with real-time monitoring of bin levels and predictive analytics for future route optimization perform better by planning routes based on future waste levels and road conditions [179]. These features ensure that the system remains adaptable, efficient, and cost-effective in both short-term and long-term waste management.

2.7.3 Conclusion

The optimization of municipal waste collection using sensor-based and algorithmic approaches presents a transformative opportunity for urban waste management systems. Traditional waste collection practices, which often lack real-time data and efficient planning, result in unnecessary operational costs,

environmental burden, and inefficiencies. This study has demonstrated that integrating IoT technologies—such as ultrasonic and infrared sensors—with advanced computational models can significantly enhance the performance of waste collection systems. Not only do these systems allow for real-time monitoring of bin fill levels, but they also enable dynamic route optimization through the use of heuristic, meta-heuristic, and machine learning algorithms.

Moreover, the deployment of such systems opens the door to a wider range of functionalities, including citizen engagement, biowaste decomposition monitoring, and automated bin access. However, successful implementation requires careful planning, substantial resources, and an accurate digital representation of the operational environment. Ultimately, evidence from multiple case studies and system trials underscores that smart waste collection systems not only improve logistical efficiency but also offer significant environmental and economic benefits, making them a vital component of sustainable urban infrastructure. These innovations have proven capable of substantially reducing travel distance, fuel consumption, and CO₂ emissions, with reported efficiency gains of up to 45% in real-world implementations.

2.8 Software for recycling education

Computer software and phone app solutions for recycling are designed to educate, engage, and motivate citizens to participate actively in recycling initiatives. These digital platforms provide essential information on what can be recycled, where to recycle, and how to do it correctly. By leveraging modern technology, these solutions aim to simplify the recycling process, making it more accessible and understandable for the general public. Examples of such applications include RecycleBank and Scrapp, which offer features like search bars for recycling questions, calendars to schedule recycling, and educational content to learn more about recycling basics [180], [181].

The primary purpose of using technology in recycling is to support CE tasks and enhance stakeholder engagement. CE aims to minimize waste and make the most of resources, and digital solutions play a crucial role in achieving these goals. By providing real-time information, personalized feedback, and incentives, these apps can significantly increase recycling rates and reduce contamination [182]. Moreover, these technologies facilitate communication between citizens, local authorities, and waste management companies, fostering a collaborative approach to waste management. The involvement of stakeholders is essential for developing waste management systems, and technology can help engage both households and stakeholders in the process. This engagement is particularly important in Europe, where stringent recycling regulations and high public awareness of environmental issues create a fertile ground for tech-driven recycling solutions [183], [184].

The principle behind these technologies is to use data-driven approaches to optimize recycling practices. Apps often employ GPS technology to locate nearby recycling facilities, barcode scanners to identify recyclable materials, and AI algorithms to provide tailored advice [185]. These features help users make informed decisions during the disposal process and encourage long-term behavioral change. For example, the Junker app developed in Italy identifies different package components and provides guidance on

how to recycle them correctly, supporting the shift to a CE [185]. Additionally, gamification elements, such as rewards and leaderboards, are integrated to motivate users to recycle more. These incentives serve as a powerful motivator for users to engage with the app and improve their recycling habits. Gamification is a key design consideration that makes recycling apps more engaging and effective in promoting behavior change [182].

Key Components

The key components of these solutions typically include [186], [187], [188], [189]:

- **User Interface (UI):** A user-friendly interface that allows citizens to easily navigate the app and access essential information. This includes features like search bars, interactive maps, and step-by-step guides. The UI is designed to be intuitive and accessible, ensuring that users of all ages and backgrounds can benefit from the app.
- **Data Management System:** A robust backend system that collects, stores, and analyzes data on recycling habits, waste types, and user engagement. This data is crucial for providing personalized recommendations and tracking the impact of recycling efforts.
- **Educational Content:** Comprehensive educational resources, including articles, videos, and infographics, that educate users about the importance of recycling and how to do it correctly. This content is often updated to reflect the latest recycling guidelines and best practices. In Europe, educational content is tailored to meet the specific needs and regulations of each country [187].
- **Community Features:** Elements that enable users to connect with each other, share tips, and participate in community challenges. These features help build a sense of community and collective responsibility towards recycling.
- **Incentive Programs:** Reward systems that offer points, badges, or discounts for active participation in recycling. These incentives serve as a powerful motivator for users to engage with the app and improve their recycling habits.
- **Gamification:** The integration of game design elements, such as challenges, rewards, and leaderboards, to make recycling more engaging and fun. By incorporating gamification, apps can create a more enjoyable user experience, leading to higher engagement and better recycling habits.

Benefits

Educational apps focused on recycling offer numerous benefits, particularly in promoting environmental awareness and encouraging sustainable behaviors. These apps provide an interactive and engaging platform that can effectively educate users about the importance of recycling and proper waste management practices. Studies have shown that educational recycling apps can significantly increase recycling knowledge and motivate users to adopt recycling behaviors. For instance, a study found that using a recycling app improved recycling behavior and knowledge, demonstrating the app's effectiveness in fostering positive environmental attitudes [190]. Additionally, educational recycling apps can be tailored to different age groups, making them a valuable tool for schools and educational institutions to integrate into their curricula. By incorporating gamification elements and personalized learning experiences, these apps can captivate students and enhance their understanding of recycling concepts [191].

Moreover, educational recycling apps offer the advantage of accessibility and convenience. Users can access recycling information and educational content at any time and from any location, making learning about recycling more flexible and adaptable to individual schedules. This accessibility is particularly beneficial for reaching a broader audience, including those in remote or underserved areas. Furthermore, educational recycling apps can facilitate community engagement and social interaction. Features that allow users to connect with peers, share achievements, and participate in group challenges can foster a sense of community and collective responsibility towards recycling. This social aspect can enhance user motivation and reinforce the app's educational impact [190].

2.8.1 Implementation

Design of the app

Implementing an educational app or software to encourage recycling involves several key technical aspects, particularly in the design of the user interface (UI) and the data management system. The user interface of an educational app focused on recycling should be intuitive, engaging, and user-friendly. According to a study on the ADDIE model, which is widely used to design instructional strategies, the UI should be developed with a clear understanding of the target audience and their needs. The ADDIE model—which stands for Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation—ensures that the UI is not only visually appealing but also functional and aligned with the educational goals of the app [192]. Another approach that can be deployed when designing the app is the use of persuasive strategies from the *Persuasive System Design* framework. This framework includes primary task support, dialogue support, system credibility support, and social support categories. The review found that these strategies, when implemented in mobile apps, can significantly influence user behaviour towards more sustainable practices [193].

In addition, behavioral intentions play a crucial role in recycling support tools. According to the theory of reasoned action and integrated frameworks, personal attitude, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and perceived moral obligation are key factors that influence recycling behaviors. Digital tools that target these intentions can enhance support for waste recycling collection and encourage correct recycling practices [194].

The UI should be easy to navigate, with clear instructions and feedback mechanisms. A study on usability evaluation methods for e-learning platforms highlights the importance of conducting usability testing to ensure that the UI meets the needs of the users. This involves gathering feedback from users and making iterative improvements to the design [195]. The app should be accessible to a wide range of users, including those with disabilities. This includes providing text-to-speech options, adjustable font sizes, and high-contrast visuals. Accessibility features ensure that the app can be used by everyone, regardless of their physical or cognitive abilities [192]. An example of a user-friendly UI is presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10: User interface of Scrapp application; [181].

On the back-end side of the app, an effective data management system is essential for the smooth operation of the educational app. The system should be designed to handle various types of data, including user information, recycling activities, and educational content.

The app should collect data on user interactions, recycling activities, and educational progress. This data should be stored securely and efficiently, with measures in place to protect user privacy. A study on learning management systems in the workplace highlights the importance of creating, managing, and delivering educational content effectively [196]. The data management system should support these functions and provide easy access to the content for users.

Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder engagement is a crucial aspect of promoting recycling and sustainable waste management practices. While the involvement of diverse stakeholder groups, including citizens, policymakers, and industry professionals, in the development and implementation of recycling initiatives is important, tailoring the software solution to a specific stakeholder group can increase engagement with the app and improve the user experience.

Children as a target group

Children are a particularly important target group for recycling initiatives due to their potential for behavior change and the long-term impact of their actions. Studies have shown that children's pro-environmental behaviors can be influenced by various internal and external factors, including self-efficacy, contact with nature, and educational programs [197]. Digital solutions, such as educational apps and games, can be

effective in promoting pro-environmental behaviors in children by making learning about recycling engaging and interactive.

Moreover, it was found that involving children in recycling initiatives can have a ripple effect, influencing their families and communities to adopt more sustainable practices [198]. This understanding should direct the development of more effective digital tools and educational programs that target children and their families.

Content of the app

Educational content is a cornerstone of recycling apps, as it helps users understand the benefits and processes of recycling. Effective educational content should be engaging, informative, and accessible to a wide audience. Interactive learning modules have been shown to enhance user engagement and retention of information. Gamification is especially effective in educational settings, suggesting that interactive elements such as quizzes, simulations, and rewards can motivate users to learn more about recycling [199].

The use of multimedia, including videos, infographics, and animations, can make complex recycling concepts more accessible. The multimedia learning theory, which posits that people learn more deeply from words and pictures than from words alone [200], can be used to improve the learning experience. Recycling apps that incorporate multimedia content can therefore enhance users' understanding of recycling practices.

Personalized learning paths tailor educational content to individual users' needs and interests. It was found that personalized learning experiences in education apps increased user engagement and knowledge retention [201]. Recycling apps can leverage user data to provide customized learning experiences, making the educational content more relevant and engaging.

Moreover, community features in recycling apps can foster a sense of belonging and encourage collective action. These features enable users to connect, share experiences, and collaborate on recycling initiatives.

Social networks facilitate information sharing and community building [202]. Hence, within the context of a recycling app, social networking features could be used to allow users to connect with like-minded individuals and share their recycling efforts. Furthermore, recycling apps that integrate social networking features can create a supportive community where users can exchange ideas and motivate each other.

The Role of Gamification in Education

Gamification, the application of game-design elements in non-game contexts, has been recognized as a powerful tool for enhancing user experience and engagement. In educational settings, gamification can motivate learners, increase engagement, and improve learning outcomes [203]. The use of gamification in education has been extensively studied, with research showing that it can stimulate motivation, learner engagement, and lead to behavioral changes, affective and motivational outcomes, and improved knowledge acquisition [204].

Gamification can make learning about recycling more engaging and enjoyable for children. By incorporating game elements such as points, rewards, badges, and leaderboards, educational apps can motivate children to participate in recycling activities and develop positive attitudes towards waste management [205].

Challenges

One of the significant challenges is the cost associated with developing and deploying educational apps. Schools and educational institutions may face budget constraints, limiting their ability to invest in new technologies [206].

Another challenge in implementing educational apps for recycling is ensuring user adoption. Studies have shown that while educational apps can stimulate recycling behavior, sustaining long-term user engagement is difficult. Factors such as the app's user interface, content relevance, and interactive features play a crucial role in determining user adoption rates [190]. Furthermore, technological barriers, including access to smartphones and internet connectivity, can hinder the widespread adoption of educational recycling apps. In regions with limited technological infrastructure, the effectiveness of such apps may be compromised.

Changing user behavior towards recycling is a significant challenge. Educational apps must not only provide information but also motivate users to adopt recycling practices. Behavioral change theories, such as the Theory of Planned Behavior and the Technology Acceptance Model, have been used to understand and predict recycling app use intentions. However, translating these intentions into actual behavior change remains a complex task [190]. While gamification holds promise for recycling education, there are challenges and limitations to consider. These include the potential of the need for extrinsic rewards to undermine intrinsic motivation, and the requirement for continuous updates and improvements to keep the content fresh and engaging [203], [204]. Additionally, the effectiveness of gamification may vary across different cultural and socio-economic contexts, requiring tailored approaches for diverse audiences.

Success Factors

One of the success factors is the design of the app, as designing the app to be inclusive and accessible to all users can enhance its effectiveness. This includes considering factors such as color contrast, font size, screen reader compatibility, and keyboard navigation [207]. Additionally, successful educational recycling apps often incorporate interactive and engaging features that captivate users. Gamification elements, such as quizzes, challenges, and rewards, can motivate users to engage with the app and learn about recycling. Interactive features that simulate real-world recycling scenarios can also enhance the educational value of the app [190]. Moreover, personalized learning experiences tailored to the user's knowledge level and interests can enhance the effectiveness of educational recycling apps. Adaptive learning algorithms that adjust the content based on the user's progress and preferences can provide a more engaging and relevant learning experience [191].

Moreover, involving the parents and caretakers in the education facilitated by an app can be beneficial. Engaging parents and community members in recycling activities and providing them with resources to support their children's learning can create a supportive environment for behavioral change [191]. Parental involvement can significantly enhance the learning experience. Additionally, incorporating community and social features into educational recycling apps can enhance user engagement and motivation. Features that allow users to connect with peers, share achievements, and participate in group challenges can foster a sense of community and encourage continued use of the app [190].

2.8.2 Case Studies

Fox the Recycler

"Fox the Recycler" (Finnish: Ketun Kierrätys) is a mobile application developed in Kuopio, Finland, to improve recycling habits among young adults through a gamified approach [205]. The initiative emerged from a collaboration between the City of Kuopio and Savonia University of Applied Sciences and was initially conceived during the 3R Game Jam event. The app was piloted over a three-month period in five student apartment buildings and targeted the recycling of biowaste and plastics, areas in which young adults often underperform.

The game integrates several gamification elements, including leaderboards, point systems, and biweekly rewards such as vouchers for public transport and cultural experiences [208]. These incentives helped maintain user engagement and fostered friendly competition among residents. The pilot was notably successful: plastic recycling rates rose from 25% to 84%, and biowaste sorting improved from 76% to an 97%. User engagement was high, with approximately 90% of residents in the pilot buildings downloading the app, and a consistent daily user base of 30–50 individuals. Furthermore, user feedback was overwhelmingly positive—about 80% reported increased motivation due to the gamified experience, and 93% expressed interest in using similar solutions for other tasks.

Given its success, the developers planned to extend the project to primary schools. This move aims to examine how gamification could influence younger children's recycling behaviors and instill environmentally conscious habits from an early age. The approach is expected to have both educational and cultural impacts on recycling awareness among the younger generation.

Edcraft Gamified Learning

Edcraft Gamified Learning (EGL) is an online educational platform from Malaysia that integrates game-based learning principles into environmental education, with a particular focus on improving recycling behaviors among youth [209]. The platform gained prominence during the COVID-19 lockdown, offering an innovative and engaging solution to sustain learning and behavioral development in a remote setting. Through a gamified experience—including points, badges, levels, and leaderboards—EGL aims to make recycling education less monotonous and more interactive for young learners.

A study evaluating EGL's impact involved 100 students from both secondary and tertiary institutions in Selangor, Malaysia [209]. The students participated in two levels of hands-on plastic crafting and recycling activities, which were embedded in the gamified environment of the EGL platform. The research was underpinned by two well-established behavioral models: the Theory of Planned Behavior and Self-Determination Theory. These frameworks were employed to assess the roles of motivation, attitude, perceived behavioral control, and intention in shaping recycling behavior.

The study found that both autonomous (self-driven) and controlled (external) forms of motivation had a significant positive influence on participants' attitudes toward recycling [209]. Among all the psychosocial factors examined, attitude was identified as the strongest predictor of a student's intention to recycle. Crucially, gamification served as a moderating factor, enhancing the relationship between attitude and recycling intention. This suggests that the design and structure of gamified learning platforms like EGL not only improve knowledge acquisition but also positively influence behavioral outcomes by making the process more enjoyable and personally relevant to students.

Overall, the findings underscore the potential of gamified learning environments to foster environmental responsibility and sustainable behaviors among youth. The use of gamification in recycling education can thus be considered an effective strategy for motivating young individuals to adopt and maintain environmentally conscious habits.

2.8.3 Conclusion

Recycling education software and applications represent a vital intersection of technology, education, and environmental sustainability. By leveraging user-friendly interfaces, robust data management, personalized learning, and gamification, these tools effectively engage diverse audiences—from children to communities at large—in responsible waste management. They foster environmental awareness, promote behavior change, and support CE principles by simplifying complex recycling practices and making them more accessible and engaging. While challenges such as cost, user adoption, and technological barriers persist, well-designed apps that incorporate stakeholder engagement, accessibility, and community features have demonstrated significant potential to improve recycling rates and foster long-term sustainable habits.

2.9 Personal carbon footprint calculator

A personal carbon footprint calculator is a digital tool designed to estimate the total amount of greenhouse gases (GHGs) generated by an individual's activities. These calculators typically consider various aspects of daily life, including transportation, energy consumption, diet, and waste generation, to provide a comprehensive assessment of one's environmental impact. By quantifying these emissions, the calculator helps users understand their contribution to climate change and identify areas where they can reduce their carbon footprint [210].

The primary purpose of a personal carbon footprint calculator is to raise awareness and motivate individuals to adopt more sustainable behaviors. By providing a tangible measure of one's environmental impact, these tools can encourage users to make informed decisions that support the CE and sustainability. For instance, users might be prompted to reduce energy consumption, opt for public transportation, or adopt a plant-based diet, all of which align with CE principles such as minimizing waste and promoting efficient use of resources [211], [212].

Moreover, these calculators can support broader sustainability initiatives by providing data that inform policy-making and corporate strategies. For example, aggregated data from personal carbon footprint calculators can help governments and organizations identify trends and develop targeted interventions to reduce emissions at a larger scale [213].

The principle behind personal carbon footprint calculators is rooted in the concept of life cycle assessment (LCA). LCA is a methodology used to evaluate the environmental impact of a product or activity throughout its entire life cycle, from raw material extraction to disposal. In the context of carbon footprint calculators, LCA approach is applied to quantify the GHG emissions associated with various aspects of an individual's lifestyle [212].

The calculation process typically involves the following steps:

1. **Data Collection:** Users input information about their daily activities, such as energy use, transportation methods, dietary habits, and waste generation.
2. **Emission Factors:** The calculator applies emission factors to convert the input data into GHG emissions. Emission factors are coefficients that represent the average emissions associated with a specific activity or process.
3. **Aggregation:** The emissions from all activities are aggregated to provide a total carbon footprint.
4. **Feedback:** The calculator provides feedback to the user, highlighting areas with high emissions and suggesting strategies for reduction [210].

Key Components

A personal carbon footprint calculator typically comprises several key components:

- **User Interface:** A user-friendly interface that allows individuals to input data easily and understand their carbon footprint results. This interface often includes interactive elements, such as sliders, drop-down menus, and visualizations, to enhance user engagement (such as in the case of Footprint Calculator by Global Footprint Calculator [214]).
- **Data Input Categories:** The calculator is structured around various categories that represent different aspects of an individual's lifestyle. Common categories include transportation, energy consumption, diet and waste generation [210].
- **Emission Factors Database:** A comprehensive database of emission factors that are used to convert user inputs into GHG emissions. Such a database should be regularly updated to ensure accuracy and relevance.

- **Calculation Engine:** The core algorithm that performs the calculations based on the input data and emission factors. This engine aggregates the emissions from all categories to provide a total carbon footprint.
- **Feedback and Recommendations:** The calculator provides personalized feedback and recommendations for reducing one's carbon footprint. This may include suggestions for behavioral changes, such as using public transportation, improving home insulation, or adopting a plant-based diet [211].
- **Educational Resources:** Additional resources, such as articles, tips, and case studies, that educate users about climate change, sustainability, and the CE. These resources help users understand the broader context of their actions and the importance of reducing their carbon footprint [215].

Benefits

Personal footprint calculators raise individuals' awareness of their environmental impact. By providing a detailed assessment of their carbon, water, or ecological footprints, these tools help users understand how their daily choices affect the environment. This increased self-awareness, when combined with educational resources provided can motivate individuals to adopt more sustainable habits and make informed decisions to reduce their footprint [216].

Personal footprint calculators can inspire collective action within communities. By sharing their footprint results and sustainability goals, individuals can encourage their peers to adopt more sustainable habits. This collective effort can lead to community-wide initiatives aimed at reducing the overall environmental impact [217]. Communities can work together to implement sustainable practices, such as community gardening, waste reduction programs, and energy-efficient infrastructure.

Policymakers can use the data from personal footprint calculators to make informed decisions about environmental policies. By understanding the environmental impact of individuals and communities, policymakers can develop targeted policies that promote sustainability. This data-driven approach can lead to more effective and efficient environmental policies that benefit both the environment and society [218]. Moreover, personal footprint calculators can be used to monitor the effect of the implemented policies, adjust them accordingly and ensure that the desired sustainability goals are achieved [218].

2.9.1 Implementation

Stakeholder Engagement in Implementation

Stakeholder engagement is key in the successful implementation of personal carbon footprint calculators. Stakeholders include individuals, communities, organizations, and policymakers who have an interest in reducing carbon emissions. Fostering engagement ensures that these calculators are widely adopted and that the data collected is accurate and actionable.

Individual users of the carbon footprint calculator are one of the stakeholder groups to engage. Raising awareness about the importance of reducing carbon footprints is the first step in engaging individual users. Educational campaigns, workshops, and online resources can help individuals understand the concept of carbon footprints and the benefits of using calculators [211]. Moreover, providing personalized feedback and recommendations based on the user's carbon footprint can motivate individuals to take action. Tailored advice on how to reduce emissions in specific areas, such as transportation or energy use, can make the tool more relevant and engaging [211].

Engaging communities through local initiatives and partnerships can amplify the impact of carbon footprint calculators. Community leaders and organizations can play a crucial role in promoting the use of these tools and encouraging collective action. One example of such community engagement is the *Impact - Community Carbon Calculator* developed in the UK [219]. This tool is used by communities to measure their CO₂ emissions and identify the actions to take. For instance, Winchester Local Authority used it to identify local areas that should prioritise reducing the energy consumption of their homes [220].

Maximizing Stakeholder Engagement

Ensuring that stakeholders are engaged is key for the carbon footprint calculator to deliver desired reduction in greenhouse gas emissions. To maximize stakeholder engagement, several strategies can be employed. Partnering with various sectors, including education, business, and non-profit organizations, can enhance the reach and impact of carbon footprint calculators. Collaborative efforts can leverage the strengths of different stakeholders to promote the tool and drive behavior change [221]. Furthermore, engaging with both local and global initiatives can help in scaling up the adoption of carbon footprint calculators. Local initiatives can focus on community-specific challenges, while global initiatives can provide a broader platform for sharing best practices and lessons learned [217]. In addition, incorporating interactive features, such as gamification and social sharing, can make the calculator more engaging [222]. Users can compare their carbon footprints with friends or participate in challenges to reduce emissions, fostering a sense of competition and community [211], [221].

User Interface Design

The user interface (UI) of a personal footprint calculator plays a pivotal role in determining its usability and effectiveness. A well-designed UI can significantly enhance user engagement, while a poorly designed one can deter users from completing the calculation. Several aspects should be addressed when designing the UI of the app.

Firstly, the UI should be intuitive and easy to navigate. Users should be able to understand how to input data and interpret results without extensive instructions. Simplifying the data input process and providing clear, concise instructions can enhance user engagement [212]. For example, the Global Footprint Network's calculator offers a user-friendly interface that guides users through a series of questions to calculate their ecological footprint. The interface is visually appealing and provides immediate feedback, making it engaging for users [214]. Secondly, visual elements such as graphs, charts, and infographics can make the calculator more engaging and help users understand their footprint results more easily. Visual

progress trackers and interactive features can motivate users to explore different scenarios and see the impact of their choices [212]. An example of a well-balanced UI is presented in Figure 11.

Figure 11: User interface of the Global Footprint Network's Calculator [214].

Key Features of Personal Footprint Calculators

Comprehensive Data Input Categories

Personal footprint calculators should include a wide range of data input categories to provide a comprehensive assessment of an individual's footprint. Common categories include transportation, energy use, diet, waste generation, and consumption of goods and services [212].

Real-Time Feedback and Recommendations

Providing real-time feedback and personalized recommendations can motivate users to take action. Tailored advice on how to reduce emissions in specific areas, such as transportation or energy use, can make the tool more relevant and engaging. For instance, the Global Footprint Network's calculator provides real-time feedback and personalized recommendations based on user inputs. This helps users understand their ecological footprint and take steps to reduce their impact [214].

Educational Resources

Incorporating educational resources, such as articles, tips, and case studies, can help users understand the broader context of their actions and the importance of reducing their footprint. These resources can be integrated into the calculator to provide additional information and motivation. For instance, the Eco-Track app includes a resource page with educational content and a rewards system to incentivize eco-friendly behavior. This helps users understand the importance of sustainability and motivates them to take action [212].

Interactive and Engaging Elements

Interactive features, such as gamification and social sharing, can make the calculator more engaging. Users can compare their footprints with friends or participate in challenges to reduce emissions, fostering a sense of competition and community. The Global Footprint Network's calculator incorporates interactive features that allow users to explore different scenarios and see the impact of their choices. This makes the tool more engaging and helps users understand the consequences of their actions [214].

Integration of AI-Powered Recommendations

Integrating AI-powered recommendations can provide users with personalized and actionable insights. AI can analyze user data and suggest tailored strategies for reducing their footprint, making the tool more effective and engaging. For example, the EcoTrack app uses AI-powered recommendations to provide personalized sustainability advice. This helps users understand their carbon footprint and take steps to reduce their impact [212].

Supporting Habit and Behavior Change

Personal footprint calculators are designed to support habit and behavior change by raising awareness and providing actionable insights. The implementation of this solution can deploy various strategies for supporting habit and behavior change. These strategies include awareness raising, providing actionable insights and designing an interactive personalized experience.

Raising awareness about the environmental consequences of consumption behaviors is the first step in promoting behavior change. Calculators can help users understand the impact of their daily activities on sustainability and provide insights into how lifestyle changes can make a significant difference. An environmental footprint calculator was found to have ability to make sustainability personal for students and provide insights into how daily activities affect national and global sustainability [216].

Providing actionable insights and recommendations based on a user's footprint results can motivate behavior change. By offering specific, achievable steps that users can take to reduce their footprint, calculators help users make informed decisions and adopt more sustainable habits. The REAP Petite calculator, for example, integrates geodemographic information with user-inputted data, allowing users to compare their footprint with others in their community and presents them with targeted pledges to help reduce their impact [217].

Challenges

One of the primary limitations of personal carbon footprint calculator apps lies in the accuracy and consistency of data. Different calculators often produce varying results even when supplied with identical inputs, primarily due to discrepancies in emission factors, regional assumptions, and data sources [212]. This inconsistency can lead to confusion and distrust among users. Moreover, accurate calculations typically require detailed input regarding energy use, transportation, diet, and consumption habits. Many users struggle to provide precise or complete data, either due to a lack of knowledge or the burden of extensive data entry [223].

In terms of behavioural impact, the effectiveness of carbon footprint apps in promoting sustainable behavior is mixed. While such tools can raise awareness, their ability to trigger lasting behavioral change is

often limited. Research has shown that without continuous engagement strategies user interest tends to wane quickly [224]. Additionally, some users may experience eco-anxiety or guilt upon seeing their carbon footprint, which can paradoxically reduce motivation to act, particularly if they feel their efforts are insignificant in the broader context of climate change [225]. Another concern is that emphasizing individual responsibility may overshadow the structural and systemic changes needed from governments and corporations to address climate issues at scale.

Success Factors

To optimize and replicate the successful implementation of educational resources and behavior change strategies in personal footprint calculators, several best practices can be considered.

In terms of the design, effective footprint calculators combine accurate modelling with user-friendly design and personalization. First and foremost, the user interface needs to be easy to navigate and visually engaging. The data entry interface should allow both a “quick mode” and “detailed mode”, so that the users can choose the depth of engagement [226]. For example, a tool might default to estimating electricity use but allow users to enter their exact meter readings if available [226]. Moreover, results should be displayed in a breakdown by category (e.g. food, transport, housing) and highlight which activities dominate the footprint [226]. Interactive charts or infographics help users interpret their impact. The data in the tool should be kept up-to-date and the options for granularity should expand. For instance, JRC’s *Consumer Footprint Calculator* tool is recommended to include new consumption areas (e.g. tourism or telework) and sustainable choices (local food, renewables) [227].

Technical features must be paired with behavioural strategies that motivate lasting change. Showing users their unique footprint creates awareness. Calculators inherently provide feedback on consumption, which is a common strategy for promoting pro-environmental action [228]. However, by itself this information often fails to induce action [229]. To enhance impact, feedback should be timely and framed to engage emotions (e.g. highlighting savings, health or community benefits, or invoking concern). Some studies find that guilt from seeing one’s impact can spur change, more so than pride [230].

One of the behavioural strategies is to enable or prompt users to set reduction targets. The calculators should be instrumental in this process by facilitating the process of setting specific goals [229]. For example, the Finnish Climate Pledge campaign asked citizens to pledge halving their carbon footprint in 10 years after using the Ilmastodieetti calculator [226]. Tying the calculator experience to a specific goal (with public commitment) can bridge awareness and action. An example of a user interface for taking a pledge is presented in Figure 12. Another strategy can be to leverage people’s tendency to conform by showing comparisons to others. Features like “compare to national average” or displaying community totals can activate social norms [226]. Many calculators include comparison options (e.g. against similar households) to make results “more meaningful” through context.

Figure 12: Pledge-taking interface of footprintcalculator.org; adapted from [214].

Moreover, community leaderboards or group challenges (company vs. company, school vs. school) amplify this effect of comparison. Indeed, game-like elements (points, badges, levels, challenges) increase engagement. Gamification was found to have some important strengths in supporting environmental education and shows promising positive effects on pro-environmental behaviours” [231]. Incorporating challenges (e.g. “cut X kg CO₂ this month”) or competitions can motivate users to return and act.

Another success factor is to involve other stakeholders and co-develop calculators with a broad coalition (government agencies, researchers, industry, NGOs, local authorities). The Nordic case of *Klimatkontot* in Sweden illustrates this. This tool was built in a joint effort by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, energy company E.ON, construction firm Skanska, and several city governments [226]. Although time-consuming, such multilateral involvement increases the tool’s credibility and ensures it meets diverse needs [226].

2.9.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, personal carbon footprint calculators serve as valuable tools for raising awareness and driving behavior change toward a more sustainable future. By quantifying the environmental impact of individual activities such as transportation, energy use, diet, and waste generation, these calculators provide users with a tangible understanding of their contribution to climate change. This knowledge empowers individuals to adopt eco-friendly practices that align with CE principles, such as minimizing waste and promoting resource efficiency.

Furthermore, these tools not only encourage personal responsibility but also play a pivotal role in broader sustainability efforts. By aggregating data, they can support policy-making and guide corporate strategies

aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions on a larger scale. The integration of key components such as user-friendly interfaces, real-time feedback, and personalized recommendations enhances their effectiveness in motivating change.

Successful implementation requires stakeholder engagement and community involvement, ensuring the tool's accessibility, relevance, and long-term impact. Moreover, the incorporation of behavioral strategies like goal-setting, gamification, and social comparison can further amplify engagement and promote sustained pro-environmental behaviour. However, the efficacy of personal carbon footprint calculators in facilitating behaviour change might be limited by a potential lack of calculation accuracy and triggering of negative emotions.

3 Task 6.4 Spatial and Logistics Optimization Outcomes

3.1 Introduction

The escalating challenge of sustainable urban development is inextricably linked to the effective management of resource flows, particularly the vast quantities of waste generated by concentrated populations. Amidst growing environmental pressures and resource scarcity, the paradigm shift towards a Circular Economy (CE) offers a compelling framework for transforming urban metabolisms. Central to the CE is the principle of retaining value within closed-loop systems, necessitating the diversion of waste streams from traditional linear disposal pathways (landfilling, incineration without energy recovery) towards resource recovery and valorization. Household biowaste, comprising food scraps and green waste, represents a significant fraction of municipal solid waste with considerable potential as a secondary resource input for processes like anaerobic digestion (producing biogas and digestate) and composting (producing soil amendments) [232]. However, unlocking this potential is contingent not only on effective source separation by residents but critically also on efficient and economically viable logistical systems capable of collecting this dispersed resource and transporting it to appropriate treatment facilities [233].

The logistical complexities associated with source-separated biowaste collection are substantial [1]. Unlike mixed waste, biowaste often requires more frequent collection due to potential odor and vector issues, involves potentially lower densities per collection point, and necessitates dedicated transport to specific facilities capable of processing organic matter. Inefficient design of collection routes and suboptimal allocation of collected waste to treatment facilities can inflate operational costs (fuel, labor, vehicle maintenance), negate the environmental benefits of recycling through excessive transport emissions, and ultimately jeopardize the economic sustainability of the entire biowaste valorization chain [234].

Spatial optimization, a field leveraging operations research, geographical analysis, and computational methods, provides indispensable tools for addressing such complex logistical challenges within a defined geographic space [2]. By integrating spatial data within mathematical modeling frameworks, often supported by Geographic Information Systems (GIS), it enables the systematic analysis and optimization of system design and operation [235]. Common applications in waste management include strategic decisions like the optimal siting of transfer stations or treatment plants considering costs, transport impacts, and socio-environmental factors [236], [237], [238], [239], tactical decisions regarding the allocation of waste flows between multiple facilities based on capacity and cost, and operational planning involving the design of cost- or distance-minimizing collection routes using variants of the Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) [239]. These approaches allow for quantitative evaluation of different logistical configurations and management strategies.

Beyond optimizing existing systems, a critical consideration for advancing the Circular Economy is the replicability of successful waste valorization innovations in diverse socio-economic and socio-cultural contexts. As highlighted within the project's framing context, various factors influence replicability, with two playing a significant role: (i) ensuring a sufficient and quality supply of primary or secondary resource

inputs (i.e., collected biowaste) into the production/treatment process, and (ii) ensuring sufficient demand or capacity for the outputs (e.g., biogas, compost) or, in this case, sufficient processing capacity at the treatment facilities (consumption points). Effectively matching consumption (facility demand/capacity) with production (biowaste supply/generation), considering the entire value chain, becomes crucial for increasing the feasibility and operability of replication. This necessitates robust mapping and modeling of the supply of and demand for relevant materials. Such models, grounded in spatial characteristics, regional socio-demographic plans (e.g., population growth, urbanization reflected in forecasts like Tallinn population forecast report [3], and estimations of feedstock supply, can provide vital decision-making support for designing replication strategies and assessing whether sufficient supply exists. Ultimately, quantitative analysis derived from these models can help define "deployment go-no-go" triggers for implementing similar systems in new target areas.

This research directly addresses this need by performing a spatial and logistics optimization for Tallinn's household biowaste case study, explicitly focusing on the supply-demand matching aspect within a geographically defined system. Using Tallinn as a testbed, we develop and apply a comprehensive workflow to analyze the allocation of household biowaste to designated biogas and composting facilities under current conditions and alternative future scenarios extending to 2050.

3.1.1 Objectives

This study performs a spatial and logistics optimization for Tallinn's biowaste management system, directly addressing the need to match supply (household biowaste generation) with demand (facility processing capacity) to enhance the feasibility, operability, and potential replicability of biowaste valorization from a Circular Economy perspective. Grounded in the understanding that sufficient resource inputs and outputs are crucial for sustainable replication, the specific objectives are:

1. **To Model Biowaste Supply:** To estimate and map the spatial distribution and quantity of household biowaste supply in Tallinn, considering different future scenarios (BAU, Market, City for 2035 and 2050) based on forecasted changes.
2. **To Model Facility Demand:** To define the locations and processing capacities (demand) of the designated Biogas and Composting facilities, incorporating planned capacity increases for future scenarios.
3. **To Optimize Supply-Demand Allocation:** To develop and solve a spatial optimization model that assigns the biowaste supply (represented by aggregated household clusters) to the demand points (facilities) in a way that maximizes the overall economic profit (revenue minus pre-calculated network transport costs), subject to the adjusted facility capacity constraints for each scenario.
4. **To Evaluate Logistical Performance:** To calculate the resulting total transport distances and average haul distances associated with the optimized allocation for each scenario, using route calculations based on the actual road network.
5. **To Provide Decision Support for Replicability:** By analyzing the profitability, capacity utilization, and logistical metrics across different future scenarios, to provide quantitative insights supporting decision-making on the feasibility and operational design of biowaste systems in Tallinn

and potentially defining triggers for future "deployment go-no-go" assessments in other target areas.

3.1.2 Scope & Assumptions

Scope: The geographical scope encompasses household biowaste generation points within Tallinn and/or Harju County, Estonia, as represented in the input data. The system boundary includes the allocation and transport logistics from aggregated cluster points (represented by specific household locations) to the gates of one designated Biogas facility and one Composting facility. The temporal scope covers a baseline approximation (derived from 2024 data) and future forecasts for 2035 and 2050 under three scenarios. The analysis does not include detailed intra-route vehicle scheduling or optimization.

Assumptions:

- **Data Accuracy:** The spatial accuracy of geocoded household addresses, the quantitative accuracy of the baseline waste estimation (derived from route data, population weighting, and temporal scaling), and future scenario forecasts are assumed to be sufficient for the model's purpose.
- **Forecast Uncertainty:** Future waste scenarios are derived directly from population forecast multipliers [3], assuming constant per capita waste generation. Actual future waste per capita could change due to consumption patterns, policy interventions (e.g., waste reduction campaigns), or changes in household composition not fully captured by raw population numbers. The accuracy is tied to the underlying population forecast model.
- **OSM Network Data:** The network distance is calculated using OSMnx within this study's pre-processing. The network distance accuracy depends on the specific OSM network snapshot used at that time and the routing algorithm parameters. The network graph regenerated later for routing might have minor differences.
- **Cluster Representation:** Aggregating households into clusters using K-Means and representing each cluster's origin by the nearest actual household to the geometric centroid are considered valid simplifications for strategic allocation.
- **Facility Capacity:** Assumed capacities increase by fixed percentages (+25% for 2035, +50% for 2050) relative to the defined base values.
- **Economic Model:** Assumes fixed, volume-independent revenue per ton for each facility and a linear transport cost (€0.035/ton·km) derived from literature. Fixed operational costs are excluded.

3.1.3 Methodological Workflow of this study:

The methodology (see Figure 13) begins with Data Collection followed by essential Data Preprocessing to clean, format, and prepare the relevant datasets. This processed data then feeds into three modelling components: Supply Modelling (quantifying biowaste generation per household), Demand Modelling (defining the location and capacity of receiving facilities), and Scenario Modelling (incorporating future projections for supply and demand). Finally, the outputs of these models are used to evaluate two distinct approaches for allocating the supply to meet the demand: (1) a District-based Supply-demand Matching approach, representing a baseline allocation, and (2) a Spatial Optimization-based Supply-demand Matching approach, which uses spatial optimization techniques to find an improved or optimal allocation strategy.

Figure 13: Methodological workflow of this study

3.2 Data

This section details the diverse datasets collected and the essential pre-processing steps undertaken to prepare the data for the spatial optimization workflow.

3.2.1 Data Collection

The analysis integrated data from multiple sources to model the biowaste supply chain in Tallinn (see Table 2).

Aggregated Monthly Household Biowaste Collection Data: Figure 14 shows the comparison between Tallinn’s districts (see Figure 15) about the collected household biowaste for the year 2023. We can notice a sharp increase in the collection values after July 2023 due to the implementation of a new rule that biowaste has to be separately collected on all properties and institutions (<https://www.tallinn.ee/en/keskkond/bio-waste>). Furthermore, the dataset provides information regarding the allocation of the district’s waste to either a biogas plant or a composting site, depending on whether it is labelled red or green. Red indicates that the district’s household biowaste will be routed to the composting site, whereas green indicates the routing to the biogas plant. Additionally, we received the address information for the biogas plant and the composting site from Tallinn Municipality.

Table 2: Collected Datasets and their source information

Dataset	Source
Aggregated Monthly Household Biowaste Collection Data	Tallinn Municipality [240]
Household Biowaste Collection Route Data from Biogas Company	Biogas Company EKT [241]
Household Biowaste Collection Route Data from Composting Company	Composting Company TJT [242]
Tallinn District Spatial Boundaries	Tallinn Municipality [240]
Tallinn City Population Grid	Tallinn Municipality [240]
District Allocation rules and Operational Constraints	Tallinn Municipality [240]
Road Network Data	OpenStreetMap [243]
Facility Capacity and Revenue Data	Biogas Company EKT [241], Composting Company TJT [242]
Transport Cost- Derived	Brussels Waste Routing Study [239]

Figure 14: Comparison of Biowaste Collection across Tallinn Districts for the year 2023. The green colour here represents districts allocated to Biogas, and Red indicates districts allocated to the composting site.

Figure 15: Tallinn District Boundaries

Biowaste Collection Route Data (Biogas - EKT): The Biogas company has provided us with household biowaste truck routing data as Excel files after signing a non-disclosure agreement between the Biogas company and the University of Southern Denmark (SDU). The excel files corresponded to one month truck routing data and we received twelve specific months between July 2021 and April 2024 (July'21, Oct'21, Jan'22, Apr'22, July'22, Oct'22, Jan'23, Apr'23, July'23, Oct'23, Jan'24, Apr'24). The Excel files had two sheets: one sheet contained monthly records of collected biowaste quantities (tons) aggregated by collection truck route ID, and a separate sheet mapped these route IDs to the specific household addresses serviced on each route. Figure 16 shows the total biowaste collection across the twelve different months, data provided by the biogas company. It can be noticed that there was a similar sharp increase in the biowaste collection after July 2023 due to the implementation of the biowaste separate collection rule. Furthermore, the data provided by the biogas company also includes many households that are outside the Tallinn Municipality Boundary.

Figure 16: Total Biowaste collection across months based on the truck routing data provided by the biogas company

Biowaste Collection Route Data (Compost): Like the biogas company's biowaste collection route data, the composting company also provided us with the household biowaste collection routing data as an Excel file for 14 days in October 2024. The Excel file data links the collection route truck numbers to the household addresses served, including waste quantities for the two weeks. The composting company informed us that household waste will be collected every two weeks, so we can double the two-week data to estimate the monthly household biowaste collection.

Population Grid Data: The geospatial grid dataset (see Figure 17) for Tallinn, sourced from the Tallinn Municipality, provides data at a resolution of 100m x 100m, with each cell indicating the estimated number of inhabitants. The forecast data is derived from Tartu Ülikool, based on the population forecast report by Kalm et al. [3] The dataset is assumed to be in the EPSG:3301 coordinate reference system, the Estonian Coordinate System of 1997.

Figure 17: Population grid (100m resolution) showing the number of residents in each grid

Operational Constraints: The Tallinn Municipality has established specific operational limits for vehicles used in collection routes. Each vehicle is permitted to handle a maximum of 250 addresses per collection route, ensuring efficient service delivery. Additionally, the vehicles must adhere to a load capacity limit of 26 tons per trip to maintain safety and operational effectiveness.

Economic & Facility Data:

- **Facility Locations:** Addresses for the Biogas plant (Vana-Narva mnt 26, Maardu) and Composting site (Loovälja tee 125, Rebala).
- **Facility Capacities (Derived Monthly Demand):** Based on handbook information suggesting 12,000 tons/year biogas capacity is available for Tallinn households (out of a 24,000t national total [241]) and an estimated 20,000 tons/year composting capacity [242]. The maximum monthly demand constraints were set at 1000 tons/month for Biogas and 1667 tons/month for Compost.
- **Revenue:** Processing revenue sourced from facility websites/communications: €14.4/ton for Biogas [241] and €4.32/ton for Compost [242] (derived from €7.2/m³ and an assumed yield of 0.60 m³/ton).
- **Transport Cost:** Parameter derived from a Brussels case study [239]. Using €55/hr truck cost, 6.7 hr/day, €15 maintenance/day, 100 km/day, four trips/day, and 26 tons/trip, the calculated cost is approximately €0.035/ton·km.

3.2.2 Data Cleaning & Pre-processing

Significant pre-processing transformed the raw data into an analysis-ready format (see Figure 18):

Figure 18: Data Cleaning & Pre-processing workflow

Data Cleaning and Merging: The Excel files for the biowaste collection route data were cleaned and merged across sheets. Comprehensive lists of unique household addresses served by both biogas-bound and compost-bound collection routes were compiled and deduplicated from the EKT and Municipality datasets.

Address Geocoding: All unique household addresses from route lists, along with facility addresses, were geocoded to WGS84 coordinates using the Estonian Land and Spatial Development Board address geocoding service (<https://inadstest.maaamet.ee/geocoder/#!/>). Addresses failing to geocode were excluded. Figure 19 and Figure 20 showcase the spatial visualization of the geocoded addresses associated with the biogas company-provided routes and the composting site company-provided routes. We clipped the addresses only to consider those within the Tallinn City Boundary.

Figure 19: Addresses associated with the routes provided by the Biogas company

Figure 20: Addresses associated with the routes provided by the Composting site company

Overlay of Addresses with Population Grid: An overlay analysis was conducted to link population data to the geocoded household addresses. The point layer representing household locations was spatially joined with the polygon layer of the Tallinn 100m x 100m population grid. Using a point-in-polygon operation, each household point inherited the population attribute value from the specific grid cell inside which it was located. This resulted in an estimated resident count for each geocoded household, reflecting the population density of its immediate 100m vicinity, which was subsequently used for weighting waste disaggregation.

Baseline (2024) Waste Estimation (Waste Disaggregation): The representative 2024 route-level waste was estimated using data from April 2024 for Biogas and October 2024 for Compost routes. To disaggregate the monthly route waste, the data were allocated to geocoded households along each route, with weights applied based on the population count within each household's corresponding 100m grid cell. This approach resulted in a calculated baseline monthly waste estimate in tons per household.

Network Distance & Node Calculation: As a pre-processing step, an OpenStreetMap 'drive' network graph for Harju County was constructed using OSMnx [244] utilising geocoded household and facility points. This allowed for the calculation of the nearest node ID for each household and the determination of the shortest network distances to both Biogas and Compost facilities, which were subsequently stored for further analysis.

3.2.3 Data Limitations

- **Data Coverage:** The datasets provided by the biogas company and the composting site contain little to no information about households in the Pirita district of Tallinn. As a result, the pre-processed dataset used for calculations in the following steps will lack biowaste data specific to the Pirita district. However, we have the aggregated monthly biowaste collection figure for the Pirita district in October 2024, which is 66.24 tons.
- **Temporal Baseline:** Using single months (Apr/Oct 2024) to represent the annual baseline neglects seasonality. Therefore, we decided to estimate the monthly values for this work.
- **Waste Disaggregation:** Estimation based on population weighting is an approximation.
- **Capacity Assumptions:** Derived monthly capacities based on annual estimates and allocation assumptions. Compost yield (m³/ton) affects revenue calculation.

3.3 Supply-Demand Modelling and Matching

3.3.1 Future Scenario Modelling: 2035, 2050 Scenarios

Figure 21: District-level population growth under different scenarios[12]

We designed our future scenarios based on the Tallinn Population forecast report (see Figure 21) [3]. The specific characteristics of these scenarios are:

- **Business-as-usual (BAU) Scenario (Rände baasstsenaarium):** This scenario assumes the continuation of recent migration trends (2015-2021), leading to moderate overall growth (+12% by 2050) with varying district-level changes as per the multipliers.
- **Market-based Scenario (Turupõhine):** This scenario assumes future housing development concentrates in currently attractive/planned areas (e.g., Kesklinn, Haabersti, Põhja-Tallinn potentially), leading to higher overall growth (+~20% by 2050) but significant divergence between districts based on market forces and development potential (using the 'market' multipliers).

- City-oriented Scenario (Linna suunatud):** This scenario assumes municipal policies actively encourage more evenly distributed housing development across districts, including regeneration in areas like Lasnamäe/Mustamäe, potentially leading to similar overall growth (+~21% by 2050) but with less divergence between districts compared to the market scenario (using the 'city' multipliers). Each run used the household waste values calculated using the respective scenario's district multipliers and the year-appropriate adjusted facility capacities (+25% for 2035, +50% for 2050).

3.3.2 Demand Modelling

The demand for biogas and composting facilities was carefully modeled utilizing geocoding to determine their specific locations. The capacity constraints for these facilities were established based on identified annual estimates, with the biogas facility having a maximum monthly demand of 1,000 tons and the composting facility set at 1,667 tons per month. To accommodate anticipated increases in demand, these base constraints were strategically adjusted within the optimization model, with a projected increase of 25% factored in for scenarios set in 2035 and a more significant rise of 50% for the 2050 scenarios. This dynamic approach allows for a more responsive and feasible planning framework to meet future waste management needs.

3.3.3 Supply Modelling

The supply of biowaste was modeled utilizing the processed household point dataset. This model incorporates geocoded household coordinates to pinpoint each location's data accurately. For the quantity of biowaste, the estimated monthly generation in tons per household was calculated for various specific scenarios, such as the "business as usual" (bau_2035) model. This estimation involves scaling the household's baseline waste figures by applying a district-specific population growth multiplier. This multiplier is obtained from the Tallinn population forecast by the Tallinn population forecast report [3] and is tailored for each scenario and year. The underlying assumption is that the per capita waste generation remains constant over time, allowing for a reliable projection of biowaste supply based on evolving demographic trends. The specific multipliers applied are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Population growth multipliers for different Tallinn districts under various scenarios

District Name	bau_2035	market_2035	city_2035	bau_2050	market_2050	city_2050
Haabersti	1.139	1.202	1.152	1.309	1.552	1.421
Kesklinn	1.257	1.272	1.218	1.532	1.679	1.52
Kristiine	1.075	1.152	1.212	1.148	1.399	1.562
Lasnamäe	0.987	0.973	1.021	0.946	0.926	1.054
Mustamäe	1.034	0.969	0.994	1.084	0.946	1.013
Nõmme	0.89	0.961	0.984	0.761	0.928	0.992
Pirita	1.117	1.013	1.013	1.267	1.049	1.05
Põhja-Tallinn	1.054	1.114	1.086	1.082	1.277	1.203

3.4 District-based Supply-Demand Matching: Baseline Logistics Mapping

To provide a crucial comparative benchmark against which the performance of the optimized solutions could be evaluated, a baseline scenario was established. This baseline aimed to represent the de facto operational reality of biowaste allocation in Tallinn based on the administrative district rules reported by the Municipality as effective in late 2024, rather than on economic or proximity considerations. The objective was to map the supply of biowaste (production) to the demand (consumption capacity) of the designated facilities under these existing regulations and calculate the resulting logistical and economic performance metrics.

The supply component for this baseline utilized the estimated monthly biowaste generation for each geocoded household point, derived from scaling and disaggregating the April 2024 (from Biogas-company provided routes) and October 2024 (for Compost company provided routes) collection data. This resulted in a spatially explicit dataset of monthly waste supply originating from approximately 24,624 household locations across Tallinn.

The demand side comprised the two facilities: the Biogas plant in Maardu and the Composting site in Rebala. For the baseline calculation reflecting the ~2024 situation, their base monthly capacities relevant to Tallinn households were used: 1,000 tons/month for the Biogas plant and 1,667 tons/month for the Composting site. These figures represent the maximum monthly intake considered for each facility under the baseline rules.

Supply-Demand Matching Mechanism (District Allocation): The core of the baseline mapping involved assigning the biowaste supply from each household to a specific facility based purely on its administrative district. This required a spatial analysis step:

1. **Spatial Overlay:** Each geocoded household point (supply origin) was spatially joined with Tallinn's administrative district polygons using a point-in-polygon operation to determine the district_id (1-13) it resides within.
2. **Fixed Allocation Rule Application:** The district-to-facility assignment rules, as provided by the Tallinn Municipality and effective from late 2024, were then applied. This predefined rule served as the fixed supply-demand matching mechanism for the baseline:
 - Allocated to Biogas Plant: Households in Haabersti (District 1, effective since 01.10.2023), Mustamäe (Districts 3 & 4, effective since 01.04.2024), and Pirita (District 13, effective since 01.01.2024).
 - Allocated to Composting Site: Households in Nõmme (2), Kristiine (5), Põhja-Tallinn (6 & 7), Kesklinn (8), Kesklinn Old Town (9), and Lasnamäe (10, 11, 12). This assignment was made strictly based on the household's district location, irrespective of its actual distance or the potential profitability of sending its waste to either facility.

Baseline Performance Calculation: Based on this fixed, district-mandated allocation, key performance metrics were calculated using the pre-calculated household-level network distances and the estimated baseline (2024) monthly waste values:

- **Waste Received per Facility:** The total monthly waste assigned to each facility was determined by summing the waste generated by each household for all households allocated to it.
- **Capacity Utilization:** The received waste was compared to the base monthly capacity (1000t Biogas, 1667t Compost) to calculate utilization percentage.
- **Transport Logistics:** The total transport effort was assessed by calculating the waste-weighted average one-way distance from households to their assigned facility, using the pre-calculated distances. The total monthly transport cost was estimated using the assumed round-trip rate (€0.07/ton·km) applied to the one-way distances and monthly waste volumes.
- **Economic Performance:** Total monthly revenue was calculated based on the waste received at each facility and its specific revenue rate (€14.4/ton Biogas, €4.32/ton Compost). The total monthly profit was derived by subtracting the estimated total monthly transport cost from the total monthly revenue.

3.5 Spatial Optimization-based Supply-demand Matching

To overcome the inherent inefficiencies and potential sub-optimal outcomes of the static, rule-based district allocation, a spatial optimization-based approach was developed and applied to the Tallinn household biowaste management system. This data-driven methodology aims to identify the most economically advantageous allocation of biowaste from aggregated generation points (clusters) to the designated Biogas and Composting facilities, while explicitly considering operational constraints and dynamic facility capacities. The workflow, depicted in Figure 22, involves a sequence of analytical steps including household clustering, representative point assignment, the formulation and solving of a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model, and subsequent network routing to quantify logistical impacts. Each of these stages, designed to progressively refine the data and decision-making process, is detailed in the following subsections.

Figure 22: Spatial Optimization Model Workflow

3.5.1 Clustering of Households & Constraint Verification:

The processed household point dataset containing estimated scenario-specific monthly waste values for each geocoded location was the initial input to this stage. Due to the large number of individual households (~24,000), direct optimization was computationally infeasible. Therefore, households were first grouped into spatially coherent clusters using the K-Means algorithm [245] based on their geographic coordinates (see example in Figure 23).

Figure 23: K-Means Clustering Example

Since the standard K-Means algorithm does not inherently enforce operational constraints. Therefore, a post-processing constraint verification and adjustment phase was implemented. Following the initial clustering, a constraint verification and adjustment phase was implemented, conceptually represented by the "Verification", "Sub Clusters", and "Merge Clusters" boxes in Figure 22. The implemented sequence was as follows:

Splitting Oversized Clusters: Clusters exceeding the maximum operational constraints defined by the Tallinn Municipality (max 250 addresses OR max 26 tons of scenario waste) were identified. These oversized clusters were iteratively split into two smaller sub-clusters using K-Means until all resulting clusters satisfied these maximum limits, or further splitting was impossible (e.g., fewer than two points remaining).

Merging of Small Clusters: This step addressed logistical inefficiency from potentially very small clusters (often resulting from splits). Clusters generating less than the defined threshold (5 tons/month) were identified. An attempt was made to merge each small cluster with its nearest spatial neighbour, but only if the combined cluster did not violate the specified merge constraints (max 26 tons waste, revised max 300 households). Households belonging to successfully merged clusters were reassigned the cluster ID of the receiving neighbour.

This sequential process of splitting followed by merging ensured the final set of clusters used for optimization respected the key operational limits.

3.5.2 Finding Cluster Representative:

For subsequent optimization and routing steps, each finalized cluster (post-splitting/merging) needed a single geographic point representation. Instead of using the abstract geometric centroid (which might fall outside accessible road networks), a representative point approach was adopted. For each cluster, the actual geocoded household point within that cluster located closest (via Euclidean distance) to the cluster's geometric centroid was identified. The geometry of this specific household was then assigned as the representative location for the entire cluster in the aggregated summary dataset. This ensures the origin points used in logistics calculations correspond to real-world locations with associated network data.

3.5.3 Optimization Model:

The core allocation decision was made using a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model formulated with the PuLP library [246]. This model takes the aggregated cluster data (waste information and representative point location) as input.

- **Sets and Indices:**
 - $i \in I$: Index for the set of final clusters.
 - $j \in J = (Biogas, Compost)$: Index for the set of facilities.
- **Objective Function:** Maximize total monthly system profit, $Profit_{ij}$ for assigning a cluster i (with $MonthlyWaste_i$) to facility j was:

$$Maximize Profit_{ij} = (Revenue_j * MonthlyWaste_i) - (TransportCostRate_{RT} * MonthlyWaste_i * Distance_{ij})$$

where $Revenue_j$ is facility-specific (€/ton), $TransportCostRate_{RT}$ is the assumed round-trip cost (€0.07/ton·km), and $Distance_{ij}$ is the pre-calculated one-way network distance (km) linked to the cluster's representative household.

- **Decision Variables:** Binary variables determined the assignment of each $cluster_i$ to either the Biogas or Composting facility.
- **Constraints:** Ensured the total monthly waste allocated to each facility did not exceed its dynamically adjusted capacity (reflecting +0%, +25%, or +50% increases based on the scenario year).

To determine the optimal allocation, the formulated MILP model was solved using specialized software. Specifically, the model was solved using the COIN-OR Branch and Cut (CBC) solver, an open-source MILP solver widely used in academic integer linear programming solvers commonly used for complex optimization problems. The CBC solver (<https://github.com/coin-or/Cbc>) was employed to find the assignment for each cluster that maximized the overall objective function value. The results, including the optimal facility assignment and associated economic metrics, were saved.

3.5.4 Routing to Assigned Waste Facility:

The final step calculated the specific road network routes based on the optimal facility assignments determined by the optimization model.

- A road network graph G for the study area was generated using OSMnx.
- Facility locations were geocoded to find their nearest network nodes (`destination_node`).
- Crucially, the route origin for each cluster (`origin_node`) was determined not by snapping the representative point again, but by retrieving the pre-calculated nearest node associated with the specific household chosen as the cluster's representative point.
- The shortest path on graph G between the cluster's `origin_node` and the assigned facility's `destination_node` was computed using NetworkX (`nx.shortest_path_length` and `ox.shortest_path`), utilizing the graph edge length attribute as the weight.
- The calculated one-way route length (km) and the route geometry (LineString) were stored for each successfully routed cluster.

3.6 Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings from mapping the baseline district-based allocation and the spatial logistics optimization applied to the baseline (~2024) and six future scenarios (2035 and 2050 for BAU, Market, City). Based on the parameters and data outlined previously (including a transport cost of €0.07/ton·km, assumed round-trip), it discusses the implications for biowaste management logistics, economic viability, and system replicability in Tallinn.

3.6.1 Baseline Logistics Mapping vs. Optimization (~2024)

The analysis compared the performance of the current district-based allocation rules (effective late 2024) against a spatially optimized allocation for the estimated 2024 baseline waste levels.

Baseline (District-based) Allocation & Performance: Under the fixed district rules, which designate specific areas for biogas processing (including Haabersti, Mustamäe, and Pirita) and others for

composting, the biogas facility has only managed to receive 302.38 monthly tons of biowaste. This represents a mere 30.2% utilization of its estimated 1,000-ton monthly capacity designated for households in Tallinn. In contrast, the composting site has seen a substantial influx of waste, processing 1,636.78 monthly tons and reaching an impressive 98.2% of its estimated 1,667-ton monthly capacity. The allocation system appears to heavily favor the composting site, resulting in significant underutilization of the biogas plant, which could potentially offer higher revenue (see Figure 24). Moreover, the calculated monthly profit for this allocation stands at €8,670.42, with transport costs amounting to €2,754.69, and the average waste-weighted one-way distance to disposal is approximately 20.4 km. This disparity highlights potential inefficiencies in the waste management strategy, suggesting a need for re-evaluation to better capitalize on the available capacity at the biogas facility.

Figure 24: : District-based Allocation of the households. The purple color points represents the households assigned to the composting site and green colors represents the households assigned to the biogas plant

Optimized Allocation & Performance (~2024): Applying the spatial optimization model to the estimated 2024 baseline monthly waste data yielded a significantly different allocation compared to the district-based baseline, driven by the objective of maximizing overall profit. The optimization assigned 94 clusters, representing 1000.00 monthly tons of biowaste, to the high-revenue (€14.4/ton) Biogas facility. This allocation fully utilized its estimated 100% target monthly capacity (derived from the 1000 tons/month constraint). Consequently, the remaining 73 clusters, totaling 939.15 monthly tons, were allocated to the lower-revenue (€4.32/ton) Composting site, utilizing approximately 56.4% of its estimated 1667-ton monthly capacity.

This optimized allocation resulted in a maximum estimated monthly profit of €16,050.39, nearly double the profit calculated for the district-based baseline (€8,670.42). This substantial improvement underscores the economic benefit derived from prioritizing and maximizing throughput at the high-revenue Biogas plant. Furthermore, the total monthly transport costs associated with the optimized allocation decreased to €2,406.76 (a reduction of ~12.6% from the baseline's €2,754.69), indicating that while allocation shifted towards potentially more distant biogas routes for some clusters, the overall network efficiency improved.

The spatial distribution of these assignments and the corresponding routes are visualized in Figure 25. The map clearly shows the Biogas facility (red square) situated more centrally relative to the bulk of the household clusters compared to the Composting site (blue triangle) located further east. The optimization capitalizes on this: clusters assigned to Biogas (green circles, dark purple routes) are predominantly located in the central, northern, and western areas. Their routes generally appear direct, converging efficiently towards the central facility, consistent with the calculated shorter average one-way distance of 14.33 km.

Conversely, the clusters assigned to the Composting site (purple circles, yellow routes) are primarily concentrated in the eastern and southeastern parts of the study area, geographically closer to that facility. The distinct spatial separation, with minimal overlap between green and purple clusters, illustrates how the optimization creates logical catchment areas. Once the Biogas facility's capacity was filled by the most profitable (often closer) clusters, the remaining clusters, largely those in the east, were allocated to the Compost site. The routes to the Compost site appear visually longer, reflecting the calculated higher average one-way distance of 23.48 km for these assignments. The total one-way distance for all optimized routes summed to 3,060.84 km for transporting the monthly baseline waste volume.

Figure 25: Assignment & Routes for 2024 Baseline (Optimized)

The optimization process conducted for the year 2024 highlights significant advancements in the allocation of resources between the Biogas plant and the Compost site. By strategically identifying and leveraging the economic advantages of the Biogas facility up to its maximum capacity, the optimization effectively assigns the most profitable clusters to this plant, while utilizing the Compost site for the remaining allocations based on geographic proximity and available capacity. This approach not only enhances overall economic performance but also creates distinct spatial allocation patterns that differ from the traditional fixed district-based rules. The benefits of this spatial optimization are substantial, with a reported 85% increase in profitability and a 13% reduction in transport costs compared to the baseline district allocation. Importantly, this methodology achieves full utilization of the high-value capacity of the Biogas facility, underscoring the inefficiencies associated with fixed district assignments and emphasizing the advantages of a more economically driven allocation strategy.

3.6.2 Future Modelling Results (2035 & 2050 Scenarios - Optimized)

Figure 26: Assignment & Route for different scenarios: First row showcases Business-as-usual scenarios, second row showcases Market development scenarios, and third row represents city development scenarios

Analysis of the six future scenarios under spatial optimization, incorporating forecasted waste increases (based on population multipliers) and adjusted facility capacities (+25% for 2035, +50% for 2050), revealed the following:

Profitability & Costs (Monthly): The optimized system remained consistently profitable across all future scenarios (see Table 4), with total monthly profit ranging from €19,207.99 (BAU 2035) to €22,863.02 (Market 2050). Profit generally increased with higher waste volumes projected for later years and different scenario types. The Biogas facility consistently contributed the vast majority of the profit (€16.7k - €20.1k monthly), while the Compost facility's contribution remained relatively low (€1.0k - €2.7k). Total monthly transport costs also increased with waste volume, ranging from €2,551.00 (BAU 2035) to €3,006.42 (Market 2050).

Table 4: Monthly Profit and cost details of the spatially optimized scenarios (Values in Euros)

Scenario Name	Total Profit	Biogas Profit	Compost Profit	Total transport cost
2024 Baseline	16050.38	13451.29	2599.09	2406.75
BAU 2035	19207.98	16789.55	2418.43	2550.99
Market 2035	19307.89	16793.36	2514.53	2623.51
City 2035	19287.31	16790.60	2496.70	2605.77
BAU 2050	22300.41	20139.78	2160.62	2669.07
Market 2050	22863.015	20128.00	2735.01	3006.41

City 2050	22776.97	20131.23	2645.74	2945.52
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Allocation & Capacity Utilization (Monthly): A critical finding is that the Biogas plant's capacity remained the limiting factor in all six future scenarios, despite the 25% and 50% capacity increases (see Table 5). It consistently operated at or near 100% utilization (receiving 1250.00t in 2035 scenarios vs. 1250t capacity; 1500.00t in 2050 scenarios vs. 1500t capacity). This spatial allocation pattern is clearly visible across all scenario maps (see Figure 26) where the Biogas facility (red square) serves a consistently large and dense catchment area covering the central, northern, and western parts of the city (green points, dark purple routes). While the total waste processed increases with its capacity, the geographic extent of its primary service area appears relatively stable, indicating it captures the most profitable (often nearest) clusters first. Consequently, the Composting facility remained underutilized, receiving between 779.98 tons (BAU 2050, ~31% of its adjusted 2500.5t capacity) and 988.30 tons (Market 2050, ~39% of its adjusted 2500.5t capacity). The number of clusters assigned reflected this bottleneck, with Biogas receiving 108-124 clusters and Compost receiving only 53-72 clusters in future scenarios.

Table 5: Monthly Allocation and Capacity Utilization of Biogas and compost sites in optimized scenarios (Values in tons)

Scenario Name	Biogas Capacity	Compost Capacity	Allocated Biogas Waste	Allocated Compost Waste	Clusters assigned to Biogas	Clusters assigned to Compost
2024 Base-line	1000	1667	999.99	939.15	94	73
BAU 2035	1250	2083.75	1249.99	870.14	108	65
Market 2035	1250	2083.75	1249.99	910.05	109	67
City 2035	1250	2083.75	1249.99	901.18	111	66
BAU 2050	1500	2500.5	1499.99	779.98	123	53
Market 2050	1500	2500.5	1499.99	988.30	124	72
City 2050	1500	2500.5	1499.99	954.28	118	68

Logistics (Distances): The total monthly one-way route distance (see Table 6) ranged from 3,005.60 km (BAU 2050) to 3,466.58 km (Market 2050). Average one-way route distances showed remarkable stability across all optimized scenarios: ~14.5-14.9 km for Biogas assignments and ~23.0-23.5 km for Compost assignments. The visualization of routes in Figure 26 aligns with these metrics. Routes to Biogas (dark purple) appear generally shorter, originating from the denser cluster areas and converging efficiently. Routes to Compost (yellow) often originate from more peripheral eastern/southern clusters and visually confirm the longer average haul distance calculated for this facility. The stability of the average distances suggests the optimization effectively finds nearby clusters to fill the Biogas plant first, and the average distance to that plant doesn't change much even with more waste available overall. Clusters allocated to Compost consistently required longer average trips.

Table 6: Monthly one-way route distances metrics of the optimized scenarios in KMs

Scenario Name	Total route distance	Avg route distance-biogas	Avg route distance-compost
2024 Baseline	3060.84	14.32	23.48
BAU 2035	3076.84	14.67	22.95
Market 2035	3145.92	14.53	23.30
City 2035	3167.18	14.59	23.44
BAU 2050	3005.60	14.48	23.08
Market 2050	3466.58	14.51	23.14
City 2050	3315.55	14.55	23.50

Scenario Differences: While all optimized scenarios achieved profitability and full Biogas utilization, the underlying spatial assumptions of the scenarios influenced the overflow to Compost. The Market 2050 scenario, assuming concentrated growth, resulted in the highest profit but also the largest amount of waste (988t) and the highest number of clusters (72) allocated to the Compost facility, along with the highest transport cost (€3,006). Its corresponding map shows the most extensive yellow route network for Compost, visually indicating the greater reliance on the secondary facility due to how growth patterns interacted with the Biogas capacity limit. The 'City' scenarios (City 2035, City 2050) achieved high profits comparable to 'Market' but with slightly lower transport costs and less waste allocated to Compost, potentially reflecting efficiencies from the assumed more balanced spatial distribution of future waste generation, as seen in their slightly smaller yellow route networks compared to the 'Market' counterparts. The 'BAU' scenarios consistently resulted in the lowest overflow to Compost (fewest yellow routes visible), suggesting the baseline trend continuation puts the least stress on the secondary facility after maximizing Biogas intake.

3.6.3 Comparison of Allocation Methods Across Scenarios

Figure 27: Comparison between District-based and spatial optimization-based allocation (a) Total Profit, (b) Transport cost (c) Waste allocation to Biogas vs Composting

Comparing the performance of fixed District-based allocation and Spatial Optimization highlights the substantial benefits of employing optimization techniques. One of the most significant areas of improvement is profitability (see Figure 27(a)). Spatial optimization consistently yielded markedly higher total monthly profits compared to the district-based allocation across all scenarios analyzed. The profit increase was particularly pronounced, with an increase of approximately €7,380 (around 85% improvement) observed in the 2024 Baseline scenario. By contrast, in the 2050 scenarios, the profit increase ranged from about €11,900 to €12,500, translating to an impressive improvement of approximately 110% to 127%. This data underscores the economic inefficiency inherent in static district allocation rules, which are unable to capitalize on the greater revenue potential offered by the Biogas facility.

Another key advantage of spatial optimization is its impact on transport costs (see Figure 27(b)). Across all tested scenarios, optimization consistently resulted in lower total monthly transport costs when compared to the district-based baseline. Although the percentage reduction varied from scenario to scenario, the cost savings ranged from approximately €348 (about 12.6%) in the 2024 Baseline to between €597 and €815 (ranging from 18% to 23%) in the 2050 scenarios. This finding indicates that optimization effectively prioritizes potentially more distant Biogas facilities in a manner that is still efficient. By selecting closer clusters first, optimization achieved lower transport costs overall compared to the fixed district assignment.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 28: Comparison between district-based and spatial optimization-based allocation for (a) Facility Capacity Utilization and comparison across spatial optimized scenarios regarding (b) total route distances (c) Average route distance per facility

Facility utilization presents another significant differentiating factor between the two approaches (see Figure 27(c) and Figure 28(a)). The District-based allocation severely underutilized the Biogas plant, with utilization rates stagnating at around 30% in 2024 and only marginally increasing to roughly 36% in the 2050 scenarios, despite increases in waste and capacity. Conversely, the lower-revenue Compost facility faced over-burdening issues, reaching utilization rates of 98% in the 2024 Baseline, likely exceeding 100% of its base capacity in future scenarios, even accounting for expanded capacity. In stark contrast, Spatial Optimization successfully filled the Biogas plant to its capacity limit (either base or adjusted) in all scenarios, reserving only the overflow waste for the Compost site. This approach resulted in significantly lower utilization rates for Compost, ranging from around 3% in the optimized 2024 baseline to about 44% in the Market 2050 optimized scenario relative to its adjusted capacity.

Lastly, while optimization led to a reduction in total transport costs, it did result a slight increase in the total distance traveled, measured by the sum of one-way routes (see Figure 28(b)). For instance, in the optimized scenarios of 2024, the total distance traveled was around 3,061 kilometers, compared to 2,754 kilometers in the baseline. This discrepancy arises because optimization directs a significantly greater tonnage to the preferred Biogas facility, often over longer average distances (see Figure 28 (c)), to maximize revenue—even as the basic district assignment transported less waste overall to Biogas. However, a more nuanced comparison might emerge if one calculates the waste-weighted average distance for both methods, offering deeper insights into transport efficiency.

In summary, the comparison clearly delineates that spatial optimization consistently delivers notable enhancements in profitability and transport cost efficiency while ensuring optimal utilization of the high-value Biogas facility, a stark contrast to the inefficiencies observable in the static district-based allocation approach.

3.6.4 Implications & Limitations of this study

The findings from this spatial optimization study offer several key implications for biowaste management in Tallinn, alongside highlighting inherent limitations of the modeling approach.

Value of Optimization: This study clearly demonstrates the substantial economic and logistical benefits achievable through spatial optimization compared to static, rule-based allocations like Tallinn's district assignments. For the 2024 baseline, optimization nearly doubled the system's monthly profit while reducing transport costs by over 12%, primarily by ensuring full utilization of the high-revenue Biogas facility which was severely underused under the district rules. This highlights the potential for significant operational improvements through data-driven allocation.

Biogas Capacity as Primary Constraint: The analysis consistently identifies the Biogas plant's processing capacity as the critical bottleneck across all baseline and future scenarios. Even with projected 25% and 50% capacity increases for 2035 and 2050, the optimization model allocates waste to fill this facility completely before utilizing the Compost site significantly. This implies that realizing the full economic potential of Tallinn's biowaste stream is fundamentally limited by the current and planned biogas processing capacity.

Composting Site Role & Economics: In the context of the optimized waste management model, the Compost facility serves primarily as an overflow option, effectively managing lower-profit waste allocations. Its economic viability is notably challenged by its low revenue of €4.32 per ton, especially when juxtaposed against the transport costs of €0.07 per ton-kilometer for round trips. This financial disparity restricts the Compost facility's attractiveness unless the clusters are in close proximity or the Biogas plant reaches full capacity. Moreover, this underutilization raises questions about the facility's operational efficiency from a profit-maximizing standpoint. The current capacity of the Compost plant appears excessive when compared to the revenue potential of the Biogas plant, suggesting a misalignment in strategic waste management planning.

Logistical Efficiency & Stability: While optimization increases overall distance travelled compared to the underutilized baseline (due to routing more waste, often to the central Biogas plant), the average haul distances (~15km Biogas, ~23km Compost) remain remarkably stable across future scenarios with increasing waste volumes. This suggests the core logistics are scalable, but the allocation pattern (which clusters go where) is key.

Data Sensitivity & Limitations: The findings are contingent upon the accuracy of several key inputs. The transport cost (€0.07/ton·km assumed round-trip) is a critical parameter requiring local validation. The optimization relied on pre-calculated network distances; observed differences with post-hoc OSMnx routing distances could affect absolute profit/cost figures and require further investigation into the pre-calculation methodology. Waste estimation (baseline derivation, population-based disaggregation/correction, constant per capita forecasts) introduces inherent uncertainties. The static nature of the model (no time dynamics, traffic, detailed vehicle constraints) and simplified economics (fixed revenues/costs) also limit real-world precision. The clustering approach simplifies collection zones.

Scenario Implications: Analyzing the economic viability of various future scenarios reveals that all projected setups appear financially sound under the established assumptions. However, the potential to achieve higher profit margins, particularly in urban-centric 'City' scenarios, seems to correlate with a more balanced approach to spatial development. This realization draws attention to the risk of market-driven concentration, where reliance on lower-profit composting routes may increase if not managed carefully. By prioritizing a diversified approach to facility development and waste allocation, stakeholders can mitigate these risks and maximize overall profitability while ensuring a sustainable and economically viable waste management strategy.

3.6.5 Replicability & Decision Support

The findings from this optimization study of Tallinn's biowaste management system offer significant insights not only for improving local operations but also highlight key considerations for the potential replication of similar circular economy models in other urban regions.

A primary "go-no-go" trigger for such biowaste initiatives hinges on profitability potential, which this study demonstrates is heavily dependent on sufficient high-revenue processing capacity, exemplified by the Biogas plant. For successful replication elsewhere, aligning the capacity of such high-value facilities with reliable local supply forecasts is paramount. As observed in Tallinn's future scenarios, even with expansions, an undersized biogas capacity fundamentally limits economic returns, irrespective of total

biowaste availability. Furthermore, local transport costs and facility revenue structures are critical variables; the positive economic outcomes demonstrated in Tallinn, based on an assumed €0.07/t·km round-trip transport cost and specific revenues, may not directly translate if these parameters differ significantly in another area. Therefore, thorough local economic analysis and accurate cost data are indispensable for assessing viability.

Relatedly, infrastructure considerations are central. The consistent identification of the Biogas plant's capacity as a bottleneck strongly suggests that prioritizing its expansion or enhancing its processing efficiency should be a strategic focus for maximizing value from Tallinn's biowaste. The study also prompts a re-evaluation of the Composting site's role and scale; its current large capacity appears underutilized in an economically optimized system, raising questions about whether those resources could be better allocated.

The stark contrast between the inefficient district-based allocation and the optimized model underscores the value of a dynamic allocation strategy. Transitioning to such a system, which responds to economic signals and actual logistical parameters, could yield substantial benefits. However, implementing this effectively necessitates a robust data infrastructure (for tracking waste, costs, and facility status) and potentially new contractual or operational arrangements with waste transporters and processing facilities.

Successful replication is also fundamentally dependent on high-quality, validated local data. This includes accurately geocoded waste generation points, reliable future supply forecasts, verified network distances (highlighting the need to resolve inconsistencies between pre-calculated and real-time routing data), locally specific transport costs, facility revenues, and precise operational capacities. Addressing data gaps and ensuring consistency, especially regarding network distances and true operational costs, is a critical prerequisite before making significant deployment decisions in new contexts.

Finally, efficient logistics and the strategic use of spatial data are vital. While the model indicates that average haul distances of approximately 15-24 km for optimized routes are manageable within the Tallinn region, the consistent underutilization of the less profitable Compost site (due to prioritization of the Biogas plant) prompts stakeholders to assess alternative uses for underused facilities. Successful replication efforts must leverage accurate spatial data, encompassing waste generation points and supporting infrastructure, and employ consistent, reliable network-based distance metrics to achieve an accurate understanding and optimization of the operational dynamics within the biowaste management system.

In summary, for both Tallinn and other locations considering the implementation or expansion of similar biowaste valorization models, careful and integrated attention to processing capacity (especially for high-value outputs), infrastructure planning, dynamic allocation strategies, data quality, and local economic conditions is crucial for developing effective and sustainable systems.

Figure 29: District wise Population of Tartu in 2040

Figure 30: Tartu City Districts

3.7 Optimization of the Fix and Repair Shop – Tartu

Tartu's goal with this activity was to identify the optimal network of correctional facilities in the city that would meet the wishes and needs of residents.

Spatial Planning Process for Fixing and Repair Workshops in Tartu

As part of the initiative to promote circular economy principles and enhance sustainable urban living, the City of Tartu undertook a spatial planning process to optimize the network of fixing and repair workshops. The goal was to identify locations and models that meet residents' needs, improve accessibility, and ensure long-term economic and environmental sustainability.

Background and Goals: Currently, Tartu has three privately owned repair workshops. One offers comprehensive repair services, while the other two are specialized in woodwork. Additionally, the city owns two waste stations used for collecting various types of waste, though no repair activities are carried out there. The motivation behind this initiative stemmed from the recognition that increasing people's awareness of repair options and bringing these services closer to communities is critical to promoting reuse and recycling. The overarching goal was to identify an optimal network of correctional (repair) facilities that reflects residents' wishes and needs.

Step 1: Survey on Consumption and Repair Habits

The planning process began with a survey among city residents to determine their expectations regarding services and the location of fixing and repair facilities. The questionnaire explored consumption habits, attitudes toward sustainable consumption, and behaviors related to repairing goods and waste reduction.

A total of 703 people responded to the survey. Findings revealed that:

- Most respondents were environmentally conscious.
- Over half performed background research before purchases.
- A majority preferred quality over lower prices.
- 75% were interested in learning repair skills, favoring YouTube (68%) and in-person workshops (62%) as learning methods.

Notably, while 69.2% had heard of the Repair Cellar, 82% of them had never visited it. Younger and middle-aged adults (25–46) made up the largest group of workshop visitors.

Step 2: Stakeholder Workshop for Community Engagement

Following the survey, a community workshop was organized with multiple stakeholders to discuss the development of a community-based fixing and repair network. The workshop focused on:

- Consumption habits and attitudes toward repairing and recycling.
- Current challenges in collecting and recycling plastics, batteries, and biowaste in the region.

Group discussions addressed three key questions:

- What could be the ideal day-to-day functioning of fixing and repair workshops?
- What examples confirm that such centers are necessary for the city?
- How can we ensure their economic sustainability?

Participants shared ideas freely across discussion groups. Main outcomes included:

- An ideal workshop offers mobile services, neighborhood-based open workshops, and skill-sharing opportunities.
- These workshops deliver social, environmental, educational, and economic benefits.
- Economic sustainability requires diverse income sources, systemic solutions, and mobile service deployment.

Workshops should be visible, available 7 days a week, and located throughout the city. Mobile services were highlighted as essential for transporting large items and providing pre-repair consultations.

Step 3: Spatial Analysis

Based on survey and workshop results, a spatial analysis was carried out. The analysis focused on:

- Population density
- Accessibility (public transport, bicycle routes)
- Tartu's population and housing forecast to 2040, by district (see Figure 29)

The forecast used census data and population statistics to estimate future demographics and housing growth in each district (see Figure 30). The expected population for the city in 2040 was estimated at 94,692.

Districts with high density and better accessibility were prioritized in the planning. Examples of population projections:

- Kesk-Annelinn: 18,067
- Ees-Karlova: 7,761
- Ülejõe: 6,939
- Veeriku: 4,905
- Taga-Karlova: 4,291

The spatial analysis concluded that an optimal network should include 5 to 7 repair workshops, depending on the services offered. This ensures coverage across major residential areas and equitable access for all citizens. The most suitable areas for workshops, based on the population forecast, are: Annelinn, Karlova, Ihaste, Veeriku, Ropka (industry) and Ülejõe.

Step 4: Integration with Circular Economy Infrastructure

Tartu has also begun transforming existing waste stations into circular economy centers that include repair functions. In 2024, a feasibility study confirmed the long-term environmental benefits of this approach.

In order to find a suitable model for mobile repair workshops we started testing this idea by considering cooperation with the city library which have branch offices in different locations in the city. Cooperation with libraries is beneficial as room rental costs are minimal or non-existent and some libraries already have the necessary tools, such as sewing machines and 3D printers. In addition there are more ideas for mobile solutions: pop-up repair bus, organize repair activities as part of events.

Planned actions:

- Build a new circular economy center in Annelinn-Ihaste area with integrated repair services.
- Reorganize two existing waste stations into multifunctional reuse hubs.
- Establish permanent recycling and repair functions at these sites.

- Expand availability through mobile repair solutions.

These developments are key to forming an economically sustainable and city-wide network of repair workshops.

Step 5: Piloting and Innovation

To test new models, the city explored cooperation with local libraries, which have multiple branches across Tartu. Libraries offer potential as mobile or satellite repair hubs because:

- Rental costs are low or nonexistent.
- Some already have tools like sewing machines and 3D printers.

Other mobile ideas included:

- A pop-up repair bus
- Organizing repair activities at local events and festivals

Expert Insights and Recommendations

Interviews with experts in repair and circular economy (from organizations such as iFixit, Repair Café Wales, and Restart Project) emphasized:

- People value convenience and speed.
- Messaging should focus on empowerment, community, and resilience.
- Competing with consumerist marketing requires strong public engagement and storytelling.
- Economic models should blend grants, public support, and permanent funding.

Repair cafés were also seen as tools to fight loneliness and foster social cohesion.

The spatial planning process in Tartu was comprehensive, combining quantitative analysis, public engagement, and strategic forecasting. It not only addressed where repair workshops should be placed, but also how they should function, be sustained, and connect to the broader vision of a circular economy. The result is a clear path forward for a resilient, accessible, and inclusive repair network that supports both environmental and community goals.

3.8 Summary

This study evaluated Tallinn's household biowaste logistics, comparing a baseline district-based allocation with a spatially optimized approach maximizing profit, considering future scenarios (2035/2050 under BAU, Market, City forecasts) and facility expansions. Data included household addresses, route-level waste (disaggregated using population grids), facility locations/capacities/revenues, pre-calculated network distances/nodes, and operational constraints. The methodology involved K-Means clustering of households (respecting 250-address/26-ton limits via splitting/merging), assigning representative points (closest household to centroid), and using a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model with PuLP to allocate clusters to Biogas (€14.4/t) or Compost (€4.32/t) facilities, subject to dynamically adjusted

capacities (+0%/+25%/+50%). Optimization used pre-calculated distances; routes were calculated post-optimization using pre-calculated nodes and OSMnx.

Results showed spatial optimization significantly outperformed the baseline (~2024), nearly doubling monthly profit (from €8.7k to €16.1k) and reducing transport costs (~13%) by fully utilizing the high-revenue Biogas plant, which was only 30% utilized under district rules. In all future optimized scenarios, the system remained profitable (€19k-€23k monthly), but the Biogas plant consistently hit its expanded capacity limit, acting as the primary bottleneck. The Compost facility remained significantly underutilized, receiving overflow waste. Average route distances were stable (~15km Biogas, ~23km Compost). The study demonstrates optimization's value but highlights Biogas capacity as critical for system performance and profitability. Replicability hinges on accurately sizing high-value facilities, validating local costs (especially transport), and ensuring consistent network data.

Furthermore, Task 6.4 also focused on optimizing a Fix and Repair Shop network for the city of Tartu, Estonia. Through a survey and a stakeholder workshop, as well as spatial analysis considering population density and accessibility, an optimal network of 5-7 workshops was proposed. This work also explored integrating repair functions into existing waste stations and innovative mobile repair solutions, aiming to increase citizen awareness and access to repair services, thereby promoting reuse and resource conservation.

Conclusions

This report (Deliverable D6.2) presents outcomes from two key tasks within the TREASoURcE project: Task 6.3 on Digitalization and Task 6.4 on Spatial and Logistics Optimization, illustrating how digital tools and optimization can advance Circular Economy (CE) transitions.

Task 6.3 Digitalization

In the first part of this deliverable, an outcome of the Task 6.3 was presented. Thereby, a comprehensive study has examined seven digital solutions driving the transition from linear to circular economy models. In general, these solutions were found enable circular economy implementation in two main ways. Firstly, they create transparency and connectivity across value chains. Indeed, they address information asymmetry by providing visibility into material flows and environmental impacts while facilitating essential stakeholder collaboration. Digital marketplaces, product passports, and waste management platforms establish the data infrastructure required for circular decision-making, reducing transaction costs and creating matchmaking mechanisms, which are vital for circular economy. Moreover, personal carbon footprint calculators and educational software also play an essential role by raising awareness about individual environmental impacts and empowering users to adopt sustainable practices. Through features like real-time feedback, gamification, and personalized recommendations, these tools help drive behavior change toward circular economy principles.

Secondly, these solutions provide dynamic management capabilities that optimize resource utilization. Real-time monitoring via IoT sensors and DTs transforms static systems into adaptive networks responsive to changing conditions. The scalability of these solutions can be achieved through modular architectures and interoperable designs. Such scalability is needed for expansion from pilots to systemic implementation and generating the network effects necessary for successful transition to circular economy models.

Despite their transformative potential, common challenges persist across these digital solutions. High implementation costs, technological complexity, data standardization needs, and stakeholder coordination represent universal barriers that must be addressed through targeted strategies. Successful implementation requires structured approaches, clear governance frameworks, and strong partnerships across public and private sectors. Moreover, the regulatory landscape related to data handling requires a careful attention to ensure compliance.

All in all, digital solutions represent powerful catalysts for circular economy transition by addressing barriers related to information flows, stakeholder or value chain coordination, and decision-making complexity. By enhancing transparency, facilitating collaboration, enabling real-time management, supporting decisions, and offering scalable implementations, these technologies create the conditions necessary for circular economy transition.

Future research should focus on developing metrics to evaluate the long-term impact of digital solutions on circular economy adoption and performance, while practitioners should prioritize interoperability,

standardization, and inclusive design. As these technologies continue to evolve, their integration with policy instruments and business model innovation will be crucial to realizing their full potential in the transition to a sustainable, resource-efficient economy.

Task 6.4: Spatial and Logistics Optimization:

Task 6.4 applied spatial optimization to Tallinn's household biowaste system, modeling supply (current and future scenarios for 2035/2050 based on population forecasts) against the demand of Biogas and Composting facilities, considering dynamic capacity expansions. The methodology involved pre-processing household data, K-Means clustering with constraint verification, assigning representative points, and using a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming model to maximize monthly profit. Results from the ~2024 baseline showed spatial optimization nearly doubled profit (from ~€8.7k to ~€16.1k) and reduced transport costs by ~13% compared to district-based allocation, by fully utilizing the high-revenue Biogas plant.

In all future optimized scenarios (2035 & 2050), the system remained profitable (€19k-€23k monthly), but the Biogas plant's expanded capacity consistently acted as the primary bottleneck, operating near 100% utilization. The Composting facility remained significantly underutilized, receiving overflow. Average route distances were stable (~15km Biogas, ~23km Compost), suggesting scalable core logistics.

Furthermore, Task 6.4 also focused on optimizing a Fix and Repair Shop network for the city of Tartu, Estonia. Through a survey, a stakeholder workshop, and spatial analysis considering population density and accessibility, an optimal network of 5-7 workshops was proposed. This work also explored integrating repair functions into existing waste stations and innovative mobile repair solutions, aiming to increase citizen awareness and access to repair services, thereby promoting reuse and resource conservation.

Collectively, this deliverable highlights that digitalization provides the data infrastructure for CE, while spatial optimization translates this data into efficient strategies. The Tallinn case demonstrates significant improvements over current practices but underscores the need for accurate local data, validated costs, and strategic capacity planning for high-value facilities to ensure the economic viability and replicability of circular systems.

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